

Masterarbeit

Accessibility of Demand Responsive Transport in MATSim: on-demand mobility's potential in peri-urban regions

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Summary

Deutsch

In der vorliegenden Masterarbeit wird die Erreichbarkeit durch *demand responsive transport* (DRT) als Form des öffentlichen Personennahverkehrs (ÖPNV) in peri-urbanen Räumen am Beispiel Kelheims untersucht. Die räumliche Verteilung der Bevölkerung und die größeren Distanzen machen den Betrieb von ÖPNV teuer und die Bündelung von Fahrtwünschen schwierig. Nicht alle Relationen und Tageszeiten werden bedient und viele Verbindungen sind mit Umstiegen verbunden. Alternative Beförderungsformen konzentrieren sich darauf, ein Mindestmaß an Service so kostengünstig wie möglich zu gewährleisten, z. B. Rufbussysteme, die von lokalen Taxis unterstützt werden. Ohne Zugang zu einem eigenen Pkw können gewünschte oder notwendige Wege nur mit einem erhöhten Aufwand realisiert werden. DRT bietet eine neue Möglichkeit auf diese Herausforderungen zu reagieren.

Das Konzept der Erreichbarkeit ist eine Möglichkeit die Mobilitätsoptionen zu betrachten. Es beschreibt die Lagegunst eines Ortes in Bezug auf den Aufwand, andere Orte und Aktivitäten zu erreichen. Die agentenbasierte Simulation MATSim sowie deren Erweiterung zur Berechnung von Erreichbarkeit wurden eingesetzt, um den Einfluss von DRT in zwei Untersuchungsgebieten in Kelheim zu untersuchen. Dazu wurden Buchungs- und Fahrtdaten des Services ausgewertet und die Komponenten einer DRT-Fahrt identifiziert. Auf dieser Basis wurden Parameter für die Erreichbarkeitsberechnung gewählt und verschiedene Szenarien bzw. Optionen vorgestellt und verglichen.

Das Potenzial von DRT zur Verbesserung der lokalen Erreichbarkeit hängt von der Anzahl und Verteilung der Zielgelegenheiten im Bediengebiet sowie der regionalen Anbindung des Bediengebiets ab. Ein dichtes Netzwerk an Haltestellen ermöglicht den schnellen und unkomplizierten Zugang zum System, dadurch sind lokale Zielgelegenheiten sehr gut erreichbar. Da peri-urbane Räume jedoch stark durch Pendlerbewegungen beeinflusst sind, ist die Anbindung aus dem Bediengebiet heraus essenziell. Der Einsatz von DRT im Pendlerverkehr weiter untersucht und die Möglichkeiten der Integration mit dem konventionellen ÖPNV geprüft werden. Entscheidend ist das Zusammenspiel der verschiedenen Formen des ÖPNV. Sie haben jeweils Stärken und Vorteile, die sich gegenseitig ergänzen können und sollten.

English

This master's thesis investigates the accessibility of demand responsive transport (DRT) as a form of public transport in peri-urban areas, using the example of Kelheim. The spatial distribution of the population and the greater distances make the operation of public transport expensive and the bundling of travel requests difficult. Not all routes and times of day are served and many connections require changing buses. Alternative forms of transport focus on providing a minimum level of service as cost-effectively as possible, e.g. call-a-bus systems supported by local taxis. Without access to a private

car, desired or necessary trips can only be realised with increased effort. DRT offers a new way to respond to these challenges.

The concept of accessibility is one way of examining the mobility options. It describes the favourability of a location in terms of the effort required to reach other places and activities. The agent-based simulation MATSim and its extension for calculating accessibility were used to examine the influence of DRT in two study areas in Kelheim. For this purpose, booking and trip data of the service were evaluated and the components of a DRT trip were identified. On this basis, parameters for the accessibility calculation were chosen and various scenarios and options were presented and compared.

Their potential is determined by the type and number of destinations in the service area as well as its connections to the larger region. A dense network of stops offers quick access to the system everywhere, making local destinations highly accessible. However, as peri-urban areas are defined by commuting and local destinations may not be available, connections outside the service area are key. The use of DRT in commuter traffic should be further investigated and the possibilities of integration with conventional public transport should be examined. The interaction of the different forms of public transport is crucial. They each have strengths and advantages that can and should complement each other.

Contents

1	Introduction	1
2	Background	3
2.1	Kelheim: between countryside and suburbia	3
2.2	Demand Responsive Transport	7
2.3	Accessibility	11
3	Data Analysis	16
3.1	Booking and General Demand	16
3.2	Spatial Demand	19
3.3	Preparation and Wait Time	20
4	Implementation with MATSim	25
4.1	Accessibility in MATSim	25
4.2	KEXI data as a basis for DRT parameters	26
4.3	First accessibility runs: train station Saal an der Donau & supermarkets .	29
4.4	The impact of wait time	33
4.5	Accessibility throughout the day	35
4.6	Service Area 6: Hausen, Langquaid, Rohr and Herrngiersdorf	38
4.7	Accessibility index of everyday needs	44
5	Reflections and conclusion	47
	Literature	i

List of Figures

1	District of Kelheim: major roads, settlements and waterways	4
2	Distribution of amenities in the town of Kelheim and in east Kelheim . . .	7
3	KEXI stops in the town of Kelheim	10
4	Routes and stop of service area no.6	11
5	Distribution of pre-booking vs. on-demand over time	17
6	Completed rides by month and booking status	18
7	Trip requests by hour and day of the week	18
8	Number of trip origins and destinations	19
9	Amenities overlaid on trip origins	20
10	Time stamps available in data set	21
11	Preparation times by month	22
12	Distribution of different "wait" times	23
13	Relationship between travel time and distance: KEXI all trips and non-pooling trips	27
14	Relationship between travel time and distance: Model run with 3 vehicles	28
15	Accessibility Train Station Saal an der Donau by DRT at 12:00 pm	30
16	Accessibility Supermarkets by DRT at 12:00 pm	31
17	Accessibility train station Saal an der Donau by PT at 12:00 pm and comparison to DRT	32
18	Accessibility train station Saal an der Donau by car at 12:00 pm and comparison to DRT	33
19	Comparisons of DRT and PT/Car accessibility of the train station Saal an der Donau at 12:00 pm using different wait times	34
20	Range of PT and DRT accessibility of doctor's offices from 08:00 to 17:00	36
21	Mean PT accessibility of doctor's offices from 08:00 to 17:00 and comparison to DRT	37
22	Mean and range of DRT and PT accessibility of supermarkets from 08:00 to 17:00	39
23	Mean DRT and PT accessibility of supermarkets from 08:00 to 17:00, measuring grid cells with buildings	41
24	Distribution of accessibility of supermarkets in settled areas by mode and municipality	42
25	Distribution of accessibility of sport facilities in settled areas by mode and municipality	43
26	Distribution of mean accessibility of everyday needs at 12:00 in settled areas by mode and municipality	45
27	Distribution of median accessibility of everyday needs at 12:00 in settled areas by mode and municipality	45

List of Tables

1	Parameters for accessibility run 1	29
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1 Introduction

The latest mobility survey in Germany (Mobilität in Deutschland, MiD) conducted in 2017, found that in the low-density areas of urban regions 51 % of all trips were made by car.¹ The spatial distribution of the population and the longer distances involved make it difficult and expensive to operate a public transport network that is attractive to all. Not all routes and times of day are covered and many connections require transfers. Alternative forms of transport focus on guaranteeing a minimum level of service as cheaply as possible, such as Call-a-Bus systems facilitated by local taxis (Rufbus, Anrufsammeltaxi)². One consequence of this can be car dependency and without access to a car or other vehicle, necessary or desired journeys cannot be made, or only with great difficulty³.

One way to talk about those potential journeys, is to consider the *accessibility* of activities. The exact definition depends on the discipline. In the social sciences, *mobility* is seen as the key to the exercise of rights; for example to education, to the labour market or to other services. Accessibility is then the result of realistically achievable mobility and the precondition for all other rights. *"It recognises the significant role of territorial or spatial mobility in the production and reproduction of social structures, in this case in relation to social welfare. Mobility and accessibility are another vector of inequality in the cities of our continent, as are processes of urban segregation or access to education.."*⁴ The issue of accessibility in the social sciences is therefore part of discussions on equality and social justice. In transport sciences, definitions that allow a quantification are common. Based on Hansen's definition, which describes accessibility as *'the potential for interaction opportunities'*⁵, important elements are accessible activities and the costs of travelling, i.e. the material and immaterial costs of overcoming space. Depending on how these elements are defined, different types of accessibility are distinguished. However, accessibility fundamentally describes the locational favourability of a place in terms of the effort to reach other places and activities.

In the context of this work, the accessibility in Kelheim, a district in southern Germany will be analysed. Kelheim has started implementing an interconnected system of demand responsive transport (DRT) services in 2020. According to the territorial classification of the Federal Institute for Urban, Land and Building Research (Bundesinstitut für Bau-, Stadt- und Raumforschung, BBSR), the region is an urbanised region, although the population distribution is very dispersed.⁶ The town of Kelheim, the seat of the district with the same name, as well as another, more rural, service area will be the focus. Neither Kelheim the town nor the other service area have a train station and apart from the DRT, the public transport consists of regional buses connecting to other towns and

¹infas Institut für angewandte Sozialwissenschaft GmbH 2018.

²Mehlert and Schiefelbusch 2017.

³Siedentop, Roos, and Fina 2013, p. 330f.

⁴Hernández 2012, p.119.

⁵Hansen 1959, p. 73.

⁶Regionaler Planungsverband Regensburg 2020.

villages in the district. The high motorisation rate reflects this⁷. Kelheim and the other municipalities are representative of many small towns and peri-urban areas in Germany. The population is spread over a large area, the neighbourhoods are mono-functional and cars are a key element of daily life.⁸

In this context, the implementation of the DRT has a large impact on the accessibility without a car. Now that trips within the service areas can be made by public transport, shopping and errands in the centres or visiting another village or neighbourhood are no longer dependent on physical capacity or access to a car. In theory it is an analogous accessibility to the private car - the DRT works similar to a taxi, it comes on demand and picks up and drops off passengers at a dense network of virtual stations. This is where the complexity of finding out how to determine the accessibility of the DRT starts, because the service is obviously not as simple as a private car. Limiting factors are for example the number of vehicles in service and the demand at the time, both in terms of quantity and destinations, which potentially result in delays or waiting times.

Although there is a lot of literature on accessibility and its evaluation in general, there has not yet been much work on ride-pooling DRT systems. The town of Kelheim, as well as the Chair of Transport System Planning and Telematics at the TU Berlin are partners in a research project investigating the use of automated vehicles as part of the DRT service. The data made available in the course of the project provides the opportunity to examine these questions. The dataset of DRT trips includes all trip requests and trip data, which makes it possible to identify demand and service quality. The spatial structure of Kelheim, characterised by dispersed settlements, promotes the use of private cars due to the lack of alternatives. The existing conventional public transport does not generate sufficient accessibility to enable a modal shift. By applying and expanding methods already documented for other transport modes, this thesis therefore proposes to identify and analyse the accessibility created by the ride-pooling DRT service. It is hypothesised that it significantly improves accessibility in Kelheim and enables citizens to make journeys previously impossible without a car.

The thesis starts with a brief description of the Kelheim study area and is followed by the state of research on DRT and accessibility analyses relevant to this work. In the following chapter the data set provided is presented and analysed with the focus on aspects relevant to accessibility. Chapter 4 describes and explains the accessibility calculations carried out, the results are visualised and explained. Finally, a brief conclusion is drawn in Chapter 5 and an outlook for possible follow-up studies is given.

⁷Bayerisches Landesamt für Statistik 2023a.

⁸Lokale Aktionsgruppe Landkreis Kelheim e.V. 2023.

2 Background

This chapter presents the study areas and their spatial structures. It offers theoretical background on DRT systems and introduces KEXI, the DRT system in Kelheim. The state of the research into accessibility calculations is presented.

2.1 Kelheim: between countryside and suburbia

Kelheim and the surrounding district with the same name are caught in a space between city and village—between urban growth and former agricultural settlements turning into suburbia. Most governmental spatial typologies fundamentally distinguish two categories: urban and rural. They can be further specified and distinguished of course, but in the end a municipality is one or the other. Administrative boundaries thereby become artificial boundaries between city and country side, as this classification inherently needs a spatial unit to perform it on. In the case of Kelheim, the district of Kelheim is categorised as rural and the municipality of Kelheim, the administrative centre, has the status of a small town. However, some of Kelheim's municipalities are described as urbanising and considered to be part of a so called "*regiopolitan urban region*"⁹. This urban region stretches between the city of Regensburg, north-east of Kelheim, to Ingolstadt in the south-west. Planning theory has attempted to find terminology for these hard-to-define, in-between spaces for decades. For example, the edge city, Zwischenstadt, ex-urban and peri-urban settlements, and the classic suburbia all exist somewhere in the midst of this spatial continuum. In the context of this work I will use the term 'peri-urban' as defined by Caruso: peri-urban areas have a rural character but are under urban influence. This *rural character* refers to low population density due to agricultural or forestry land use, 'urban influence' refers to strong links to an urban centre including significant commuting.¹⁰

In 2022 the district of Kelheim had a population of ca. 125 000, which is a population density of about 118 inhabitants/km², in 24 municipalities.¹¹ For comparison: Germany has a population density of 234 inhabitants/km².¹² The town of Kelheim is the largest municipality with ca. 17 000 inhabitants. Four more are of a similar size, each between 12 000 and 16 000 inhabitants. All other municipalities are considerably smaller, making for an overall quite dispersed population.¹³ The urban regions surrounding Ingolstadt and Regensburg include the northern and eastern municipalities. The southern half of Kelheim is classified as a rural area in the vicinity of an urban region, with two municipalities being described as urbanised. The classification as a regiopolitan urban area points to a functional connection between Kelheim and the closest cities. Criteria in the study were a travel time of 30 minutes or less by car or a commuter share of 25 %

⁹Bundesinstitut für Bau-, Stadt- und Raumforschung 2019.

¹⁰Caruso 2001, p. 12.

¹¹Bayerisches Landesamt für Statistik 2023b.

¹²Statistisches Bundesamt 2024.

¹³Bayerisches Landesamt für Statistik 2023b.

Figure 1: District of Kelheim: major roads, settlements and waterways

or more.¹⁴¹⁵ In total nearly 50 % of employed residents commute outside of the district, mostly to Ingolstadt and Regensburg.¹⁶ The official data shows that the few municipalities with a positive commuter balance either have a significant amount of manufacturing industries or so called public and private sector service jobs. The latter includes all forms of public administration; many of those jobs are centralised in the town of Kelheim, where both the town and district administrations are located. Only about 600 people work in agriculture or forestry. Therefore, in terms of economic structure, the district is similar to firmly-established suburban districts closer to the larger cities.¹⁷ Kelheim's spatial structure however, defined by a few small towns, a widespread network of villages and, most importantly, a widely spread out population, brings a lot of the issues rural communities face.

The adverse consequences that a low population and dispersed settlements have for public transport networks have been documented in a variety of contexts and places.¹⁸

¹⁴Bundesministerium für Verkehr und digitale Infrastruktur 2018.

¹⁵Bayerisches Landesamt für Statistik 2023c.

¹⁶Landratsamt Kelheim 2018.

¹⁷Bayerisches Landesamt für Statistik 2023c.

¹⁸i.e. BMVI 2016; Wehmeier n.d.; International Transport Forum n.d.

One of the more obvious aspects is the difficulty to run a cost-effective public transport system that suits everyone, when there is a lower demand but larger distances to travel. The last mobility survey in Germany (Mobilität in Deutschland, MiD) from 2017 found that in rural regions, about 70% of all trips are made with a private car.¹⁹ And with good reason—not all relations and hours of the day are covered by public transport and many trips require time-intensive interchanges. The focus is on transporting students to and from school, which is a main source of funding, but doesn't necessarily reflect the needs of the population.²⁰ The goal is usually to guarantee a minimum level of service in the most cost-effective way. A common solution in Germany on low-demand routes is to implement Call-a-Bus type solutions, however, they usually have to be called with a lot of notice—in some cases at least 24 hours in advance. Therefore, without access to a private car or other motorised vehicle, not all desired or even necessary trips can be made and in many cases only with comparatively high effort. About 20 million people in Germany live in areas similar to Kelheim²¹, on the borders of regiopolitan regions that are urbanised but not yet categorised as 'urban'. Finding new solutions could mean facilitating social and economic integration as well as improving the sustainability of travel in low-density regions.

The local development strategy of Kelheim describes the accessibility by public transport and cycling as insufficient. The lack of connections between residential neighbourhoods and town centres is listed as one of the weaknesses in the SWOT analysis, linked to the closing of shops on the high street in favour of an expansion of shopping centres and commercial development on the outskirts of town. The term 'doughnut effect' is used to describe new residential and commercial developments that have grown around the historic town centres, implying a draw of population but also resources into the outskirts. Despite this the expansion into formerly agricultural lands continues and is also considered an opportunity for attracting young families. Kelheim is a touristic district; the historic town centres, hiking and bike paths along the rivers and various landmarks in the immediate surroundings all attract visitors. To improve their options for getting around, the so-called *Leisure Bus* connects major attractions during the summer months. During the rest of the year public transport is limited to low-frequency regional buses which connect the larger towns and surrounding villages to the cities in the region. Their main objective, however, is to transport children to school, so outside of school hours there are few departures. KEXI and the *Leisure Bus* are highlighted as opportunities and a good basis for better public transport, but the strategy paper does not foresee a reduction of trips in private cars, which it links to the insufficient connections to larger urban centres.²²

The town of Kelheim itself is situated at the confluence of the Danube and the Altmühl River, on both banks as well as the peninsula formed between them. The towns Ihrlerstein

¹⁹BMVI 2018.

²⁰BMVI 2016, p. 12.

²¹Statistisches Bundesamt 2023.

²²Lokale Aktionsgruppe Landkreis Kelheim e.V. 2023, p.37.

and Saal seamlessly border to the north and south-east, forming a continuous urban structure. Kelheim's city centre and old town are located on the peninsula, and a shopping centre is located further north at a large intersection. Directly south of the city centre, a mixed-use office park including supermarkets and medical practices has been developed. Connecting Kelheim and Saal is a large industrial and commercial area. The urban structure is defined primarily by single-family homes and a few small apartment buildings along residential streets that have been built around historic villages. The rivers form a significant barrier between the neighbourhoods; only two bridges connect the southern bank with either the old town or the northern bank. The old town is well connected to the adjacent neighbourhood to the north, although only for foot and bike traffic.

Figure 2, a map of amenities, shows clusters in the old town, around the shopping centre and the office park. The aim of the amenities, sourced from Open Street Map, is to represent daily necessities. They include the categories supermarkets, other groceries (i.e. bakeries), doctors and health (i.e. pharmacies and drug stores). Work is not included as a category as there is no reliable data regarding the exact location and number of workplaces, and neither is education, as that is the one activity that has guaranteed accessibility through school buses. The individual amenities visible are either supermarkets or doctors' offices. To include one leisure aspect in the analysis, sports facilities were also mapped. They are of interest to the DRT analysis as their spatial distribution greatly differs from the other amenities, and they are more likely to be located on the outskirts of town where accessibility by conventional public transport is lacking. In Kelheim the main sport complex, including a swimming pool, several gymnasiums and sports fields, is located near the geographical centre of town. A second one lies at edge of town, near the industrial area.

The second map shows the other area of interest: four municipalities to the Southeast of the town of Kelheim. It's characterised by many small villages, regularly distributed around an area of about 14 x 15 km. The largest settlements are Langquaid in the Northeast and Rohr in the Southwest. The total population of the area is around 13 000²³. More than 75 % of the working population commutes to surrounding municipalities or the larger urban centres Regensburg and Landshut, each about 40 km away²⁴. While many villages have a local football or shooting club, there are few other amenities. Three out of four municipalities have at least one supermarket and two have at least one doctor. Public facilities includes places like town halls, libraries, post offices and community centres. Like the town of Kelheim they are part of the regiopolitan region of Regensburg. However, the local development strategy criticises the lack of connection with public transport, which forces commuters to use private cars²⁵. Kelheim is one of the districts with the highest motorisation rates in Germany and these municipalities are no exception; in January 2024 there were around 8 700 private cars and 1 300 motorbikes registered. It can likely be assumed that all households with the economic means and physical capabilities have at

²³Bayerisches Landesamt für Statistik 2023a.

²⁴Bayerisches Landesamt für Statistik 2023c.

²⁵Lokale Aktionsgruppe Landkreis Kelheim e.V. 2023, p. 38.

Figure 2: Distribution of amenities in the town of Kelheim and in east Kelheim

least one motorised vehicle. Those reliant on public transport are therefore those too young or old to drive, people with disabilities, and households with very low income. In the next years this group is predicted to grow district-wide: the number of people over 65 is going to grow by nearly 40 percent by 2042, and specifically in Langquaid it will rise by over 60 percent. At the same time, it is assumed that a continued influx of families will also raise the share of children. The current system based on private cars will become insufficient for many and threaten their accessibility of everyday necessities, requiring a rethinking of local public transport.

2.2 Demand Responsive Transport

Demand-responsive transport (DRT), is a possible way of organising public transport in a low-demand context to improve accessibility. Simply put, DRT refers to a transport system that is responsive to demand. It suggests the possibility of deviating from timetables and routes based on changing demand. Call-a-Bus and collective taxi services are common in Germany, wherein a route or a stop is only served if the passenger has called ahead. Overall, the service still relies on a general route and a timetable, but the operator has the option to optimise it based on the travel requests, saving resources. From a user's point of view, these services can be unattractive because their frequency is usually low and they need to be called with sufficient anticipation. Increased computing capacities and digitalisation, however, make completely free-floating systems possible. Here, vehicles do not follow routes or timetables, but rather travel requests made via an app are matched

with a vehicle through an algorithm. These requests can also be combined and rides pooled. In the following the term DRT will always assume a free-floating, ridepooling system.

While there were attempts at creating such a system as early as the late 1970s, the technical capacities of the time did not scale with the financial resources available and thus the project was stopped.²⁶ Now the most well-known transport services to use these algorithms are Uber and Lyft, offering non-ridepooling services in various German cities, including public transport companies. The focus of these ridepooling services is usually to offer transport options late in the evening and at night, and in the case of those run by public transport companies, also on transporting passengers from and to areas with otherwise little public transport connections.²⁷ Private companies have identified a profitable market in and around city centres. In the case of Hamburg, Aberle²⁸ has shown that the areas where these private companies choose to operate have a denser, younger population less likely to be receiving social benefits, and have overall decent public transport infrastructure. Using a combination of their licensing rights and subsidies, the municipality got one company to include a more remote and economically disadvantaged neighbourhood in their service area, thus improving the connection to the next train station. As the cooperation is still ongoing and being intensified²⁹, it can be assumed that this is a profitable decision. So, while without the usual public transport subsidies, this service might be too expensive to run, or the potential ridership may be lacking the financial means, a subsidised ridepooling service might be more cost-efficient than organising fixed bus lines.

A pilot project in Amsterdam, described in a paper by Coutinho et al.³⁰, suggests the same. Fixed bus lines in a very low-density part of Amsterdam were replaced with a free floating DRT service which improved vehicle utilisation and significantly improved operating costs. Large buses were replaced with smaller, cheaper vehicles requiring less fuel, and while the cost per kilometre rose, the cost per passenger dropped considerably. However, making this change also caused a drop in ridership from about 78 passengers daily to 16. While these remaining passengers were very satisfied with the service, especially its punctuality, it raises the question of why two thirds of the former passengers did not switch to the new service. One possible reason is that booking was made via an app, and another may be that the pick up would be planned in a 15 minute window around the desired departure time; this is impractical in the case of fixed appointments or transport connections. Sørensen et al., in their evaluation of a DRT service in rural Lower Saxony, found similar: to guarantee a ride at a specific time, many users would book their rides in the mornings, blocking most of the day and not leaving any flexibility for spontaneous bookings.³¹ In this case, the solution was a maximum pre-booking time

²⁶Mehlert and Schiefelbusch 2017, p. 31.

²⁷CleverShuttle 21.07.2023; MOIA 21.07.2023; BVG 2024, i.e.

²⁸Aberle 2020.

²⁹ioki 2023.

³⁰Coutinho et al. 2020.

³¹Sørensen et al. 2021, p. 17.

of an hour, which left capacity for spontaneous bookings, but meant that people would only know an hour beforehand if their ride would get them somewhere in time or not. These examples are meant to illustrate briefly some of the aspects of switching to a DRT system. Alonso González et al. have collected these and more aspects and developed a framework to assess DRT systems in general.³² Their goal is to be able to analyse the improvement in mobility based on observed usage patterns, but they also break down the components of the system influencing that usage very clearly. They highlight five criteria when describing the system characteristics: coverage and routing, operating hours, vehicle characteristics, booking system and request acceptance criteria. While the first three are likely key from the operator's point of view, the results from Amsterdam and Lower Saxony show that the booking process and request acceptance criteria might be equally as important to the users; in the case of fixed bus lines, these are straightforward and reliable after all.

In the next section, as well as some of the data analysis, the framework developed by Alonso González et al. will be used to discuss and analyse the DRT system in Kelheim. The DRT system KEXI started operating in the town of Kelheim in 2020.³³ It did not replace an existing bus network but acts as an addition to regional bus lines. Analogous to those the commissioning body of KEXI is the district council and the contractors deliver the service. Since then it has been expanded to several other towns in the district as well as most rural areas. In most service areas it runs as a free-floating service with operating hours between 6:00 and 20:00 or 23:00. There is no service on Sundays and public holidays. Each of the service areas operates independently with around 1 000 stops in the district in total; some of them overlap and permit changes between services. The fleets are made up of between two and three small wheelchair-accessible buses with seats for a maximum of 6 passengers. In addition to the conventional vehicles, some stops in the town of Kelheim are served by an automated vehicle as part of the research project KelRide. Through KelRide, some of the KEXI data was made available for this work. Rides can be booked either via an app or through the phone, however, due to changes in contractors the app has changed several times. Rides can be booked up to seven days in advance and while there is a suggested lead time of 30 minutes, this is not a requirement. The website does not provide any information about the possibility of rejected ride requests. However, the data shows that when a ride request can not be fulfilled at the desired time, another time slot may be offered. The criteria for this new time slot are unclear.

This work is going to consider two service areas in detail: the town of Kelheim and service area no. 6 of the so-called *Land-KEXI*, or rural KEXI. There are about 150 stops in the town of Kelheim and one at the train station in the neighbouring municipality of Saal. The stops in town have a maximum distance of 250 m between them, so while this is not a door-to-door service, it minimises walking distances. The rest of Saal and other adjoining municipalities are not part of the service area, despite the mostly seamless development.

³²Alonso-González et al. 2018.

³³Landkreis Kehlheim n.d.

The area is served by a maximum of three vehicles at the same time. Compared to the regular public transport tickets, the DRT costs about one Euro more for all journeys; as of September 2024, it costs 3 € to travel within Kelheim and 4 € to go to Saal. Children and senior citizens pay 2 and 3 € respectively.³⁴ The Deutschland-Ticket is valid, so the cheapest fare possible is 49 € per month. The Figure 3 shows the distribution of the stops; those in orange are also stops of the automated vehicle.

Figure 3: KEXI stops in the town of Kelheim, source: Landkreis Kehlheim n.d.

Service area no.6 of the rural KEXI encompasses the four municipalities presented earlier in this Chapter. In Figure 4, this area is defined by a purple outline. Unlike the service area in the town of Kelheim, it is not a fully flexible service. Instead, the official paperwork published by the district of Kelheim contains the basic framework of a timetable and a route map. Departure times from the first stop on the route are scheduled, whereas the other stops depend on pre-booked trips, but they are always served in the same order. In this way, the service area is served by two one-directional looped routes that mainly function as a connection to the two largest villages. They each run seven times a day and are best described as a highly digitised Call-a-Bus service. If not using the Deutschland-Ticket, there is a base price of 2,50 € and each kilometre costs an additional 0,40 (adults) or 0,35 € (discounted). The first of the following maps is published by the district. The blue lines represent the potential routes including detours to villages slightly off the main road. The second map is taken from the KEXI website and only shows the stops themselves. The slightly transparent blue (or purple) polygons in the first map describe the catchment area around each stop. It is assumed that the catchment areas cover 9 351 people in total, 4 934 of whom did not have access to public transport before.³⁵ It is unclear why, but the website does not mention that the vehicles follow specific routes and times; the FAQ section only explains how the free-floating service works. When attempting to book a trip that does not correspond to the routes,

³⁴cf. Verkehrsgemeinschaft Landkreis Kelheim 2024.

³⁵Ibid., p. 36ff.

the app displays a message informing the user that there are no rides for this connection available, but again the underlying issue is not explained. A search in the online archives of the local newspapers as well as the municipal websites could not find a description of this system either. Despite this, simply based on the numbers, it seems like a major improvement from the situation before.

(a) Official map of service area no.6, source: Landkreis Kehlheim 01.05.2023 (b) KEXI stops in service area no.6, source: Landkreis Kehlheim n.d.

Figure 4: Routes and stop of service area no.6

2.3 Accessibility

Accessibility and its evaluation have been topics of research since at least the 1920s. Different disciplines, including urban and spatial planning as well as transport engineering, consider the topic from various perspectives. Using the keyword 'accessibility' in a search using Web of Science results in nearly 8000 works in English in the areas of transport, urban studies and geography. The following will summarise the field of study with a focus on the evaluation of accessibility and only insofar as it relates to the subject at hand.

An early and much-cited definition of accessibility was developed by Hansen (1959), working for the Bureau of Public Roads in the United States of America. According to him, accessibility describes *“the potential of opportunities for interactions”*.³⁶ He underlines the importance of the intensity of the interactions, not just the ease of them, thus distinguishing a difference between what could be referred to as simple and complex accessibility.³⁷ The main objective of Hansen's work was the modelling of metropolitan growth. He theorised that accessibility is a key factor in explaining the spatial distribution of growth and urban expansion. To this end, he created a model to calculate the accessibility for all places and compared it to the accessibility of all *other* places. The model was meant to be used in the process of planning new public infrastructures.

³⁶Hansen 1959, p. 73.

³⁷cf. Schwarze 2014, p. 43.

Monzón de Cáceres follows a similar idea in his work from 1988. His aim is to create an evaluation process of public infrastructure measures to better observe their effects. To him, “*accessibility indicates the ease with which a given land use can be reached from a given location using a transport system.*”³⁸ He emphasises the relevance of the destinations of each journey, focusing on the satisfaction of everyday needs since his goal is the homogeneous development of the region. His definition explicitly mentions the transport system, although in his work he only considers one mode, the car, because his work evaluates different proposed motorway developments. Both works are examples of the use of accessibility calculations: they can prepare and inform government decisions and also allow for subsequent evaluation.

Over the years, several authors have proposed ways to categorise and compare accessibility measures. Still much-cited internationally are the works by Handy and Niemeier from 1997³⁹ and Geurs and van Wee from 2004.⁴⁰ In a German context, the works by Schwarze should also be mentioned.⁴¹ Particularly in his dissertation from 2014, he extensively describes different accessibility measures and expands on the advantages and disadvantages of their practical applications with a focus on their comparability and communication with the public. He mainly differentiates between simple and complex accessibilities, describing simple accessibility measures as those that focus on modelling individual parameters of the transport system or the settlement structure.⁴² Geurs and van Wee refer to these as infrastructure-based accessibility measures.⁴³ Both works stress the popularity of these accessibility measures in transport policy as key performance indicators and ways to communicate with the public.⁴⁴ The main focus of all three works, though, are the so-called *complex* accessibility measures; those that link transport systems to land use. Schwarze breaks them down mathematically as a construct of two functions, one describing the opportunities accessible from a certain point and the second the effort needed to overcome the space in between:

$$A_i = \sum_j g(W_j) f(c_{ij}) \quad (1)$$

A_i describes the accessibility at the point i , the function $g(W_j)$ the opportunities at the destination j , and the function $f(c_{ij})$ the cost of travelling from i to j .⁴⁵ The choice of functions and their relation differentiates different measures. Geurs and van Wee add a temporal and an individual component to the definition.⁴⁶ The temporal component is

³⁸“... la accesibilidad indica la facilidad con la cual un determinado uso del suelo puede ser alcanzado, desde una localización determinada, usando un sistema de transportes.” Monzón de Cáceres 1988, p. 22.

³⁹S. L. Handy and Niemeier 1997.

⁴⁰Geurs and van Wee 2004.

⁴¹e.g. Schwarze 2014.

⁴²Ibid., p. 46.

⁴³Geurs and van Wee 2004, p. 131.

⁴⁴Schwarze 2014, p. 46; Geurs and van Wee 2004, p. 131.

⁴⁵p. 53 Schwarze 2014.

⁴⁶Geurs and van Wee 2004, p. 128ff.

described as reflecting temporal constraints; those of the transport system or the activity, but also on a personal level. This connects to the individual component which is meant to reflect personal characteristics like needs, abilities and opportunities affecting their relation to all of the other components.⁴⁷ It would exceed the scope of this work to discuss all accessibility measures described, the one used in this work, a utility measure, is described in Chapter 4.

Accessibility measures should be chosen based on the situation at hand: Handy and Niemeier, in the chronologically first paper, discuss the process of developing and evaluating an accessibility measure to fit a specific project. Regardless of the type of measure chosen, the degree and type of disaggregation as well as the definition of origins and destinations will strongly influence the results. The question of disaggregation arises for all components of the measure; the spatial extent (zone, household,...), the activities (i.e. work vs. white collar work), the time frame (i.e. all day vs. peak rush hour) and population considered (everyone, separated by income, gender,...). Up to a point, a finer disaggregation will likely lead to a more accurate estimation of accessibility, but only as long as the data quality remains sufficient and always at the cost of calculation speed.⁴⁸

Until now, all mentioned works have been concerned with spatial accessibility, meaning the connectivity and reachability of places. Origins and destinations are most often implicitly chosen and also interpreted as representing home and an activity. The accessibility of the home is assumed to be representative of the accessibility overall.⁴⁹ This is reasonable in the sense that the mobility options at the place of residence influence the mobility behaviour for the rest of the day.⁵⁰ However, this logic also has clear limitations: it only accurately represents the accessibility of places and activities starting from the specific place of the home and cannot accurately reflect the accessibility of persons with long activity chains. For example, a neighbourhood might have low accessibility to shopping opportunities, but those residents who work in the city centre will in reality have a very high accessibility to shopping opportunities if they combine them with their work trip. In the case of groups with longer activity chains, the real accessibility might therefore differ considerably.

Individual accessibility measures attempt to overcome this problem, explicitly taking into account the personal needs and preferences of the population, especially with respect to the feasibility of the trips within the necessary time frame. Some of the most influential works on individual accessibility are those by Kwan, who has been working on the topic since the 1990s. In her work from 1998, she criticises the use of spatial accessibility to represent the accessibility of individuals or social groups.⁵¹ She argues that it has already been established that different people consider the accessibility of the same place differently based on their personal needs and abilities. On top of this, spatial-temporal

⁴⁷Geurs and van Wee 2004, p. 128ff.

⁴⁸cf. S. L. Handy and Niemeier 1997, 1178f.

⁴⁹cf. *ibid.*, p. 1179.

⁵⁰cf. S. Handy 1996.

⁵¹Kwan 1998, p. 192.

restrictions heavily influence accessibility when it comes to long activity chains. Kwan examines accessibility for men and women by comparing the results of a spatial accessibility computation with those of an individual accessibility computation, following the idea of time-space prisms by Hägerstrand. The space-time framework suggests that in activity chains there are fixed stops (i.e. home, work) and in between those there are flexible stops (i.e. shopping) that can be performed in a spatial-temporal prism that is limited by the time available and the space accessible. The results of the individual accessibility computation show strong differences between the sexes that the spatial accessibility computation is unable to reproduce. Kwan writes: *“In the final analysis, personal accessibility is mediated by the process of choice and spatio-temporal constraints circumscribed by the situational complexities of a person’s daily life in a particular sociospatial context.”*⁵² Although she sees great advantages in the use of individual accessibility, she agrees with Handy and Niemeier as well as Schwarze when it comes to the selection of accessibility computations in practice: it needs to be based on the question at hand and a perfect solution for all situations doesn’t exist.

There has been little literature regarding the accessibility of a DRT system similar to the one implemented in Kelheim so far. There are some papers measuring accessibility improvements by automated on-demand transport⁵³, however they all assume a significantly larger fleet and don’t consider ridepooling. The main issue when attempting to estimate DRT accessibility as opposed to other public transport, is that its routes and times are not fixed, but dependant on demand. Travel time therefore fluctuates and is only calculated in the moment when a trip is requested. A dataset of DRT trips, real or simulated, therefore can never contain enough information to estimate accessibility for all relations and times. Ziemke and Bischoff, estimating non-pooling DRT accessibility, used MATSim’s ability to simulate both dispatch times and private car accessibility and combined the two.⁵⁴ However, this required running the simulation enough times and with enough vehicles that dispatch times would be simulated for all observed cells. Most likely, the first paper explicitly dealing with ridepooling DRT as public transport is currently in pre-print. Diepolder et al. developed a method to estimate accessibility based on MATSim simulation data⁵⁵. The accessibility measure used is isochrone-based, which in other literature is referred to as cumulative accessibility. Its definition is simple and easy to communicate, which makes it a popular measure used in urban planning. Using a fixed travel time (in the case of Diepolder et al., 60 minutes⁵⁶) the number of reachable opportunities is counted, the more opportunities are reached, the better the accessibility.⁵⁷ Diepolder et al. aim to offer a new approach to using simulation data, proposing a solution to the issue faced when attempting to use previously observed trips for accessibility computations. They refer to it as *‘a spatial-temporal statistical pipeline to*

⁵²Kwan 1998, p. 213.

⁵³Meyer et al. 2017, i.e. Nahmias-Biran et al. 2021; Ziemke and Bischoff 2023.

⁵⁴Ziemke and Bischoff 2023, p. 751.

⁵⁵Diepolder et al. 2024.

⁵⁶Ibid., p. 7.

⁵⁷S. L. Handy and Niemeier 1997, p. 1177.

*transform a dataset of previously observed [DRT] trips in a graph representation*⁵⁸ which they implemented in Python. Before the work on this thesis started, the same issue was discussed and a solution was found using a newly developed DRT estimator by Lu. It is discussed briefly in Chapter 4, but is not part of this work. Another paper dealing with a smaller DRT system and using real service data considers the accessibility of a non-pooling public DRT system for people with disabilities in Seoul, Korea⁵⁹. They defined the accessibility by the availability of empty vehicles which they calculated for different zones and time slots.⁶⁰ Accessibility here therefore describes the ease of accessing the transport system itself. It remains unclear if in those times and spaces of low availability, there is a demand that exceeds availability. While vehicle availability is a key factor in DRT accessibility, it cannot define it on its own. The work is an interesting approach, however, to analysing DRT systems in general.

⁵⁸Diepolder et al. 2024, p. 2.

⁵⁹Son et al. 2022.

⁶⁰Ibid., p. 3f.

3 Data Analysis

This dataset contains 206 258 ride requests between June 2021 and August 2024. About 40 % of the requests could either not be satisfied at the time or the user rejected the ride proposal. Another 11 % were accepted but not completed; they may have been cancelled or the passenger(s) did not appear for pick-up. 92 354 (45 %) rides were marked completed, meaning the passenger or passengers were picked up and brought to their destination. There were changes in the booking process in January 2024, which meant that for a time there were different apps for the automated vehicles (AV) and the conventional DRT. This dataset only contains those requests made through the app for the AV service. In order to obtain a consistent dataset for any general analysis, these are only included in AV specific questions. After filtering out rides with ride times shorter than a minute or longer than 30 minutes (assuming those are recording errors), 91 453 rides were left between June 2021 and December 2023. Most rides were booked for a single traveller, about 17 % were booked for groups of up to 8 travellers. In the following analysis, only rides are considered, not the number of travellers.

3.1 Booking and General Demand

Bookings were made by 4 213 unique user IDs, however about a third only made a single trip and another third up to six trips. The ten most frequent users, on the other hand, account for about 11 % of all completed trips. 65 users account for 33 %. It becomes obvious that while many people have tried the service at least once, not many continue using it regularly. Some of them might be tourists who have no opportunity to do so, others however are locals who have decided against it. Regarding the booking method, the app has become slightly more popular over time, but booking via an agent is still relevant as it accounts for about 15 % of all trips. What has changed, however, is the booking type: over time, the number of on-demand bookings has decreased and more trips are being pre-booked.

This may correspond with the increase in unavailable seats over time. In an interview, the head of the district transport department stated that with the current number of vehicles, the number of transported passengers had reached its natural limit.⁶¹ This limit appears to be between 3 000 and 3 500 passengers a month. The ride requests in total, however, rose significantly, and in September 2023 there were more than three times the number of requests than completed rides. A closer look at the data reveals users unsuccessfully trying to book an on-demand ride, then re-trying for a slightly later time, sometimes repeatedly until they get a seat. This both increases the number of requests and likely also affects their booking behaviour in the future. According to the case study described by Sørensen⁶² the on-demand aspect of the ride-hailing service was not working the way it was intended or expected. Instead, users' need for reliability causes more and more people to pre-book, essentially recreating a conventional timetable-based service,

⁶¹Weigert 29.10.2024, p. 2.

⁶²Sørensen et al. 2021.

Figure 5: Distribution of pre-booking vs. on-demand over time

albeit with more personalisation.

Month-to-month variations in ride requests can also partly be explained by the ticket costs, with highs in June, July and August 2022 coinciding with the 9€-Ticket and the increase in May 2023 with the start of the Deutschlandticket. The dip in February, March and April 2023 in both rides and ride requests has not been explained. The extreme rise in trip requests starting September 2023 only partially coincides with a rise in individual user numbers, suggesting mostly an increase in repeated attempts to book a seat. The original trigger for this behaviour is unclear, but the sudden onset suggests a change in the DRT system (either the app or the booking process) as a cause.

Looking at the demand throughout the day offers more detail regarding the unfulfilled ride requests. It makes sense that the number of unavailable seats is higher during times with overall high demand like the early afternoons. However, the number is actually highest early in the morning, when the demand is at or below average. This likely has to do with the number of drivers on shift, as similar demand in the evening is able to be fulfilled. The spike in the morning — that also has a slight mirror in the evening — might suggest some people using the service to commute to and from work. A closer look into the destinations does show some people travelling into industrial areas, but overall the spatial distribution is very dispersed and resembles the destination distribution overall, which aligns with the distribution of amenities. This isn't however an argument against some of those trips possibly being work trips, as all amenities are also workplaces. The higher number of unaccepted proposals during the day may insinuate that users are checking their options and either deciding to book later or use different public transport. The number of ride requests per week day follow an expected pattern that also shows up in national mobility surveys: fewer trips on Monday, highs on Wednesday and Friday and

Figure 6: Completed rides by month and booking status

again fewer trips on Saturday.⁶³

Figure 7: Trip requests by hour and day of the week

⁶³BMVI 2018, p. 26.

Using a shortest path algorithm to calculate the distance⁶⁴, the trips average a length of around 3 km. Longer trips are those to and from the train station and to the Hall of Liberation ("*Befreiungshalle*"), a monument on the peninsula between the rivers west of town. The length of trips stays reasonably constant over time and is slightly longer in the mornings and evenings, coinciding with a higher share of trips to and from the train station. The trip duration (which is included in the dataset) averages slightly below 9 minutes and overall corresponds with the trip duration. Trip distance and duration are further explored in Chapter 4.

3.2 Spatial Demand

Figure 8 shows the spatial distribution of origins and destinations. The trips are spatially joined to a 200 x 200 m grid placed over Kelheim and counted for each cell. The data also includes trips that start or end outside of the service area, as users can also input specific addresses rather than just stops and the system chooses the closest stop for them.

Figure 8: Number of trip origins and destinations

The majority of trips originate and terminate in a limited number of cells. The noticeably yellow one in the east is the location of the train station in Saal an der Donau, and the one slightly northwest of the map centre is a shopping centre. Together with the stops in the town centre they are the most common origins and destinations; about 42 000 trips either originate or end here.⁶⁵ To better understand the impact of land use,

⁶⁴Pereira et al. 2021.

⁶⁵This extreme clustering of trips is the reason why origins and destinations were mapped separately instead of as a flowmap. The flows to and from the train station and shopping centre overwhelm any other relation and no other information is gained.

Figure 9 shows the amenities — as well as specifically supermarkets and sports facilities — overlaid on the trip destinations, allowing a direct comparison between the two.

Figure 9: Amenities overlaid on trip origins

Amenity clusters overlap with popular destination cells and most individual amenity points are in the vicinity of green cells. As most users book their trip to a specific stop rather than an address, in cases where the amenity is some distance away from the nearest stop, it is the cell that contains the stop that is green, rather than the cell that contains the amenity. This can be observed for example in the case of the supermarket nearly in the centre of the map: the closest stop (and therefore the closest green cell) is about 500 m away. The second map also shows that not all amenities are as likely to influence DRT demand. While the literature⁶⁶ has shown that people will use it disproportionately for leisure activities, in Kelheim, sports facilities are not a reliable indicator for DRT demand. The main sports complex, with its cluster of athletic fields, swimming pool and gymnasium, has a very popular DRT stop right in front of it. The closest stop to the athletic fields on the eastern edge of town, however, has fewer than 40 trips ending there. A closer look at the data also reveals that most of those trips were actually made by the same two people. This mirrors general user behaviour — few users generate most of the trips — and also explains the lone green cell south of the river in a residential area where around 3 000 trips start and end: 28 % of those are just two users.

3.3 Preparation and Wait Time

A major component of overall trip time and therefore accessibility are the preparation and wait times. Preparation time here refers to the time between making the request

⁶⁶Knie et al. 2020; Zwick and Axhausen 2022, i.e.

and the requested departure time, i.e. the time frame the user decided is necessary to prepare the trip. It is not in itself part of the trip duration, but is a key step in the process of using DRT that sets it apart from other modes which don't necessarily require a preparation phase.

Figure 10: Time stamps available in data set

There are more ways to define the wait time. This data set contains the requested departure time⁶⁷, the originally planned departure time, the last planned departure time, the time the user was texted that the vehicle had arrived and the time the user actually boarded the vehicle. The majority of trips, about 40 %, have a requested departure time within 5 minutes of the time of the request. Because the user wants to presumably begin their journey as soon as possible, everything after the requested departure time could already be considered waiting time. As seen earlier, more and more trips are labelled as being pre-booked. While there is no clear preparation time associated with that label, the share of trips with a preparation time shorter than five minutes has fallen and the share of those with a preparation time longer than 30 minutes has risen. The possibility to pre-book for up to 7 days is used by very few users, but booking a trip for significantly later in the same day has become more popular.

A difference between the requested and originally planned departure time happens when the ride request can not be satisfied at the requested time, but instead within a certain time frame either earlier or later, and the user then accepts this alternative departure time. This time period is called 1st planned delay in the graphic. For about 30 % of trip requests, requested and originally planned departure time are the same. Another 40 % have a planned departure time that is between 5 minutes earlier and 10 minutes later than the requested time. Looking at the distribution of these values it seems likely that in most cases a difference of more than 30 minutes means that the ride request is rejected by the service and no alternative is offered. The impact of a planned delay on the user depends on the trip purpose and the person's overall plan for the day. In the case of trips that are flexible in time a planned delay can be inconvenient and somewhat unpredictable before booking, but the time can be repurposed and will typically not be spent actually waiting. When booking trips to a fixed appointment, i.e. to work or to catch a train, the planned delay does have a significant impact on the trip duration. The

⁶⁷Less than 2 % of trip requests are made not with a requested departure time but a requested arrival time. These trips are not included in the analysis using the requested departure time.

Figure 11: Preparation times by month

solutions for the user are to either book an earlier time when possible or to wait at the place where their prior activity has terminated.

The adjusted planned delay is the result of the app updating the planned departure time dynamically. This dataset includes the last communicated departure time, but not when it was communicated nor how many changes there were. For the overwhelming majority of trips, the planned departure time either doesn't change at all, or not by more than two minutes. However, this time period should be included in the wait time. On the one hand, not all users receive this information (those who book by phone do not) and on the other, even if the users are informed of a delay, they are unlikely to be able to meaningfully repurpose this time.

About 83 % of trip requests include the vehicle arrival time, permitting a calculation of the vehicle delay. This time is equivalent to waiting at the bus stop in a conventional, timetable-based system and, and is the most inconvenient for the user. Interestingly, in the case of KEXI the vehicles are more likely to arrive before both the original and planned departure times rather than after, and very few have a delay of more than 10 minutes. Taking into account departure time updates, vehicle delays are nearly eliminated. Despite the fact that many vehicles arrive a few minutes before the planned departure times, most passengers board within two minutes. This time stamp is generated by the driver and therefore subject to human error. It is likely that in some cases the boarding is recorded late, as some ride times are very short when compared to their ride distance. Overall, the short boarding times suggest that passengers are already waiting at the stop when the vehicles arrive, making a predictable departure time even more important.

The assessment framework proposed by Alonso González et al. includes several overall system performance measures. Four of them can be directly applied to the KEXI data:

Figure 12: Distribution of different "wait" times

the share of declined trips as a reliability indicator, the shares of walkable and bikeable trips realised with the DRT service to assess competition with active modes, and the share of DRT trips connecting to regional transport. The share of declined trips has already been discussed earlier in this chapter: It has risen significantly over time and in December 2023 was at 40 %. For a service that is the main public transport in town, this is a very high number. In a next step it would have been interesting to calculate the share of declined trips for different spatial relations. Sørensen et al found in their study that longer rides and those connecting to other towns were much more likely to be declined than short ones within town.⁶⁸ This makes sense, as shorter ones are more easily fitted in between pre-booked trips and cause less of a detour for the driver. To calculate the shares of walkable and bikeable DRT trips, the mean walk and bike distances in Germany (1.7 km and 3.9 km respectively⁶⁹), were compared to the trip distances. Considering the size of the service area and the rise in pre-booking, it is not surprising that only 9 % of trips are shorter than 1.7 km. In many cases, walking is likely to be the quicker alternative. About 69 % are shorter than 3.9 km and therefore technically bikeable, however the town has some hilly neighbourhoods, so more people than usual might decide against it for physical reasons. The added independence and flexibility of biking might however still make it a faster alternative. As there are no integrated booking options, to assess its connectivity with regional transport the only indicator is the number of trips to and from the train station in Saal an der Donau. While some trips might be to Saal itself, around 20 % of trips start or end there and may therefore connect to regional transport. Again, a higher reliability might raise this number even further. Not part of Alonso González et al.'s framework, but very relevant to evaluate the effectiveness

⁶⁸Sørensen et al. 2021, p. 13.

⁶⁹infas Institut für angewandte Sozialwissenschaft GmbH 2018.

of the service, is the ridepooling rate. In this dataset 47 % of completed trips are also marked as shared, which is high compared to the 20 % pooling rate in the similarly rural setting described by Sørensen et al.⁷⁰ Coutinho et al. calculate an occupancy of 0.630 by dividing passenger kilometres by vehicle kilometres.⁷¹

The data shows a system close to its limits. At peak demand many ride requests cannot be fulfilled and users are forced to rebook for later. At the same time, once booked, the service is punctual, and if one is using the app it communicates any delays. This varying reliability is likely the cause for many users not using the service more than a few times. Those who can arrange themselves with and around it, maybe because of a more flexible daily schedule or simply a lack of other options, use it several times a week and it is very likely that a larger number of vehicles and drivers would find a rising demand due to improved service. The demand for better regional public transport connections to larger urban centres described in the local development strategy⁷² is echoed in the number of trips to and from the train station in Saal an der Donau. Increasing the frequency of the fixed bus lines running between Kelheim and the train stations might take some of the strain off KEXI and make those longer-distance trips more predictable.

⁷⁰Sørensen et al. 2021, p. 13.

⁷¹Coutinho et al. 2020, p. 7.

⁷²Lokale Aktionsgruppe Landkreis Kelheim e.V. 2023, p. 37.

4 Implementation with MATSim

A central idea for this work is to explore the possibilities offered by the multi-agent transport simulation software MATSim for the calculation of accessibility. The publicly available, calibrated model for Kelheim offers a lot of the required data and MATSim itself a fast way to execute the calculations. With the accessibility contribution for MATSim developed by Ziemke, there is already an implemented method to calculate the accessibility from the run results. The only thing missing is the ability to do this for the mode DRT. In a collaborative process between Ziemke, Rehmann and Lu it was determined that if assumptions were made about the relationship between travel distance by car and travel time with DRT, the travel times for all DRT trips could be estimated.

4.1 Accessibility in MATSim

Like the travel choices in MATSim the accessibility contribution is based on random utility theory. In a general MATSim run, simulated agents follow their prescribed daily plans, which contain activities at specific locations and trips in between those. At the end of the day, the executed plans receive a score based on the time their time spent and may be adjusted regarding mode choices or start times with the goal to maximise it. The utility score increases when they reach their planned destinations on time and decreases while travelling and when they are running late. For the scoring, time spent, monetary costs and aspects like comfort while travelling are converted into so-called utils, creating comparable values from disparate parameters. So when it comes to accessibility, the accessibility of an activity is also measured in utils and influencing factors are travel time, cost and mode-specific utility parameters. To offer a frame of reference to interpret the results, an hour of any travel time is usually valued at -6 utils in MATSim.

This concept of accessibility used draws on the analysis by Geurs and van Wee, who identify four necessary components in the measuring of accessibility: land-use, transport, as well as a temporal and an individual component⁷³. In regards to land use, this means that all activity opportunities are considered—not only the nearest one. The components of transport and time include factors like time needed for interchanges or delays due to high traffic volume. The quality of the individual component depends highly on the data available. Geurs and van Wee describe it as reflecting *'the needs (depending on age, income, educational level, household situation, etc.), abilities (depending on people's physical condition, availability of travel modes, etc.) and opportunities (depending on people's income, travel budget, educational level, etc.) of individuals.'*⁷⁴ As MATSim is agent-based, this information can be included, however in most cases only a small subset of it exists and is available for use. In the case of Kelheim, all personal information is 'synthetic', meaning while it accurately represents the population as a whole, the individual plans and characteristics have been shuffled and there is no real knowledge gain in taking them into account.

⁷³Geurs and van Wee 2004, cf.

⁷⁴Ibid., p. 128.

The accessibility calculation has the following form:

$$A_\ell := \ln \sum_k e^{V_{\ell k}} \quad (2)$$

A_ℓ describes the accessibility at location ℓ , while "[...] k goes over all possible destinations, and $V_{\ell k}$ is the disutility of travel in order to get from location ℓ to location k . [...] This so-called logsum term has an econometric interpretation as the expected maximum utility (e.g. Ben-Akiva and Lerman, 1985)."⁷⁵ In the case of DRT and public transport $V_{\ell k}$, the negative cost associated with travel is made up of four components:

- duration and distance of access walk: measuring point to transport stop,
- duration and distance of trip: transport stop to transport stop
- duration and distance of egress walk: transport stop to activity
- the alternative specific constant (ASC) associated with the transport mode.

The duration and distance of each component are multiplied with mode-specific parameters, converting time and distance into utils. These parameters as well as the ASC are automatically taken from the calibrated model, but can also be adjusted if desired. The measuring points are freely specified as a grid and permit highly granular results.

In the case of public transport, several stops are considered and the one offering the fastest trip to the destination is used as the access stop. For DRT the closest stop is always chosen; it is assumed that the DRT vehicles are optimally distributed and the difference in trip duration would be negligible as the additional walk time and a shorter DRT trip would cancel each other out. For car trips, the agents 'walk' to the nearest link that permits car traffic and start their car trip there. They drive as close to their destination as possible and walk from the link to the coordinates of the activity. An important caveat is that in MATSim the mode 'walk' is teleported, meaning that it does not get routed through the actual street network. The distance is calculated based on the Euclidean distance multiplied by a detour factor, which is meant to represent the structure of the actual street network. In the case of Kelheim the detour factor is 1.3, but with its rivers, this is still a flaw, as in some cases it is assumed that agents will teleport across them to an activity or DRT stop that is technically close by, ignoring the fact that there is no bridge. For a detailed accessibility analysis of the town of Kelheim this would need to be adjusted. In the context of this work it is sufficient if one keeps this in mind.

4.2 KEXI data as a basis for DRT parameters

The missing components to calculate the DRT accessibility are the travel time and the travel distance. The travel distance is calculated based on the direct network distance for

⁷⁵Nicolai and Nagel 2014, p. 4.

cars. The corresponding travel time can vary depending both on the travel speed but also on the actual route taken, which may deviate from the shortest route to accommodate other passengers. To estimate this longer travel time a linear regression model is run on both real-world data and results from a model run and the parameters describing the relationship between shortest travel distance and actual travel time are estimated. The original idea was to estimate the parameters from the KEXI data to accurately calculate the accessibility specifically created by the service. The cleaned data from Chapter 3 was filtered to only include trips provided by conventional vehicles, which have a more reliable speed and as before, a shortest path algorithm was used to calculate the shortest possible travel distance in car from origin to destination⁷⁶. Figure 13 shows first all KEXI trips and then only non-shared trips, visualising the issues with the data.

Figure 13: Relationship between travel time and distance: KEXI all trips and non-pooling trips

In both cases, travel distance only explains a small part of the variation in travel time and the cause is only partly the shared rides. Even in non-shared rides, which should be a direct trip with minimal delays through traffic, the travel time varies wildly. To give an idea of the variability, for the most popular relation, train station to shopping centre and vice versa, the travel time varies between 5 and 20 minutes on a distance of about 6 km. One reason might be the option to take different routes with different speed limits, but another is some aspect of driver behaviour: When grouping the non-shared rides by driver and building separate linear regression models, R^2 ranges from around 0.16 to 0.42, meaning that for some drivers travel distance explains travel time a lot better than for others. As the travel time in the data set is defined by the boarding and alighting times, both of which are recorded manually by the driver, differences in their routine might explain this variation. It has to be assumed that the recorded travel time is not identical to the actual travel time, as in the time that the vehicle moves from origin to destination, but that it might for example include the process of boarding and alighting, which differs from passenger to passenger. All that said, estimating the parameters based on the actual KEXI data is hard to justify. While β_1 , the slope, is quite consistent, the

⁷⁶Pereira et al. 2021.

intercept β_0 varies and has a high standard error in all the linear models built on the KEXI data. At the same time, due to its size it has a considerably higher influence on the results than β_1 , making it a main determinant of any result.

The other option is to estimate the parameters based on the results of model runs, where it is guaranteed that the travel time is always calculated the same way. The results shown in the next graphic are from a Kelheim MATSim model run with three vehicles, representing the current KEXI service. Again, the distances don't include detours to pick up or drop off other passengers. The travel time, however, is the actual travel time, including detours. Overall travel times are shorter, which would support the theory that travel times in the KEXI data include time that is not spent travelling. The travel distance also explains more of the travel time and β_0 is smaller, giving more influence to β_1 and therefore the distance. Repeating this process with other model runs with different seeds returns very similar values.

Figure 14: Model run with 3 vehicles: $\beta_0 = 71.82$, $\beta_1 = 0.119$, $R^2 = 0.44$, $n = 172$

In another context the relationship between travel time and distance could also simply be called speed. However, speed usually suggests that both travel time and distance can be zero. There is no minimum travel time before any distance can be overcome. β_1 seems like it is describing speed (or rather the inverse of it), but it only exists in combination with β_0 which describes a minimum travel time. No matter how small the distance travelled, any trip takes at least β_0 seconds. β_0 absorbs a part of the travel time created by possible detours, but also some of the vehicle speed itself, for which β_1 then has to compensate. So for very short trips, the estimated travel time is likely somewhat too high and for longer trips slightly too low.

4.3 First accessibility runs: train station Saal an der Donau & supermarkets

To run the first accessibility calculations, the parameters wait time, β_0 and β_1 , as well as a destination, need to be defined. Based on the demand it makes sense to consider the train station. This also has the added advantage that looking at just one destination makes the results easier to interpret. In the first step all parameters are taken from the model run and the model configuration, resulting in the following values:

name	value	origin
ASC	2.45 utils	Kelheim model configuration
utility of distance DRT	-0.00025 utils/m	Kelheim model configuration
performing utils	-6 utils/h	Kelheim model configuration
wait time	422 s	Kelheim model output
β_0	71.82 s	Kelheim model output
β_1	0.119 s/m	Kelheim model output

Table 1: Parameters for accessibility run 1

The utility of travelling between any measuring point and the destination(s) is calculated in two parts: the utility of travelling from the measuring point to the destination stop, and the egress walk from the destination stop to all the destinations to which it is closest. Very brief and simplified, the utility of the DRT trip, or $V_{\ell k}$ in (2), is calculated as follows:

$$utility_{access} = time_{access} * performingUtils$$

$$utility_{DRTtime} = (waitTime + \beta_0 + \beta_1 * directRideDistance) * performingUtils$$

$$utility_{DRTdistance} = directRideDistance * utilityDistanceDRT$$

$$utility_{DRT} = utility_{access} + utility_{DRTtime} + utility_{DRTdistance} + utility_{egress} + ASC$$

Consequently, when only considering one destination, such as the train station in this case, the DRT accessibility at any point is equal to $utility_{DRT}$

Upon a first glance, the calculated accessibility looks to be overall very good; slightly higher closer to the train station and lower further away from town. On a second glance, however, some counter intuitive details emerge: the areas with the best accessibility are not directly around the train station, but in the industrial areas between Kelheim and Saal an der Donau. The reason behind it lies in the way the accessibility is calculated. For trips where the access and egress stop are the same, such as in the area around the train station, it is assumed that the mode chosen is 'walk'. The same is also true for trips where the accessibility by DRT would be lower than the accessibility by foot. This mainly applies to areas directly around any destinations. So in this case, the accessibility is highest in the industrial areas, because the DRT stops there are closest to the train station. Another question that arises is how the accessibility, which is defined by the cost of travelling, can be positive. The reason is the ASC for DRT taken from the model configuration; resulting from the calibration with real data, it is 2.45. This is unusual and

Figure 15: Accessibility Train Station Saal an der Donau by DRT at 12:00 pm, wait = 422, $\beta_0 = 71.82$, $\beta_1 = 0.119$, $R^2 = 0.44$

can be interpreted as users that have an increased interest in this mode that is greater than their dislike of travelling. In the case of Kelheim, with the lack of viable alternatives on many relations in combination with comparatively cheap tickets, it might also simply describe the interest in a better public transport option in general.

The positive ASC is also one of the reasons why the accessibility of supermarkets is distinctly positive in all of the service areas. The others are the distribution and increased number of opportunities. Supermarkets are distributed around the town and on both sides of the river, making the distance to at least one supermarket much shorter than the distance to the train station. Additionally, the higher number of opportunities increases the possible maximum accessibility, because as seen in (2) the accessibility to each opportunity is added together. In terms of interpretation one can say that this shows great accessibility of supermarkets by DRT. This is, however, an interpretation with very little context. It says nothing about the alternative modes and makes assumptions about the meaning of utils as a measure of accessibility.

Figure 16: Accessibility Supermarkets by DRT at 12:00 pm, wait = 422, $\beta_0 = 71.82$, $\beta_1 = 0.119$, $R^2 = 0.44$

Figure 17: Accessibility train station Saal an der Donau by PT at 12:00 pm and comparison to DRT

To further investigate, it therefore makes sense to consider the other modes.

For easier comparison, the train station is considered again. The map for public transport (PT) shows an overall lower accessibility with the only light green area being located right around the train station. From there, accessibility gets lower in a circular gradient. This gradient pattern shows up in areas where walking is the fastest mode of transport and accessibility diminishes as the distance grows. On the western and northern side of Kelheim there are abrupt changes of accessibility caused by bus departures. Within a radius around the bus stop, the next departure can still be reached. Outside of that radius, one would have to wait for the next bus. There are a few of those abrupt changes of accessibility in the map due to the low frequency of the buses. These island patterns around bus stops change depending on the exact time for which the accessibility is calculated. In the case that walking is quicker than both DRT and PT, the difference in accessibility is zero; this can be observed in the area around the train station. Again, due to the low frequency of PT, fewer bus stops in general as well as the higher ASC, DRT has a higher accessibility even quite far outside of town and the DRT service area. Similarly to the DRT maps, the mean and range of the accessibility values are given for comparison purposes, however to improve the space utilisation of the page the map view is slightly smaller for all side-by-side maps and the extreme values might not be visible.

The accessibility by car is close to zero utils around the train station and gets lower with increasing road distance from there. As opposed to the accessibility by DRT, it is never positive, and while they are close to equal around the train station, in most parts of the city it is lower. Again this is due to the difference in ASC: Up to a certain

Figure 18: Accessibility train station Saal an der Donau by car at 12:00 pm and comparison to DRT

distance from the service area the higher ASC of the DRT balances out both wait times and increased walk times and distances. Without the positive ASC, the accessibility by car would always be higher than the accessibility by DRT as DRT cannot travel faster than a private car and has additional wait times and detours. Here, the interpretation of what this increased utility means is especially important. If the higher ASC describes a population that has an increased interest in the mode DRT, this means that for this population the accessibility by DRT is on average better than the accessibility by car. This measure does not represent the population as a whole. Accessibility here takes into account not only time and distance but also soft factors like comfort, not having to drive oneself or flexibility. Those who do not consider the DRT in such a favourable light are unlikely to consider the accessibility to be higher than by car.

4.4 The impact of wait time

As discussed in Chapter 3, the definition of wait time is an important part of defining the trip duration for DRT. The wait time calculated in the MATSim model is based on the time between booking the ride and the arrival of the vehicle. The model only includes on-demand booking, so the assumption is that agents book a ride and then wait at the side of the road until the vehicle comes to pick them up. On a practical level, this wait time is most similar to the time period between the last communicated departure and the vehicle arrival time in the KEXI data set. The user is only waiting and cannot use the time any other way. As seen earlier, for KEXI this period is usually quite short, often even negative, meaning the vehicle arrives early. The low delays caused by passengers

also show that users usually profit from these early arrivals, therefore it makes sense to include these cases up to a point, even if they significantly lower the average wait time. Considering only rides where the vehicle arrived less than 10 minutes early, the average length of this wait is around 15 seconds. Another option is to look at the wait times of on-demand trips in the KEXI data. Solely based on the definition, this time frame is most similar to the model: the user wants to travel as soon as possible and any time until the vehicle arrival time is considered wait time. For trips with a preparation time of less than 5 minutes, the average time difference between the requested departure time and vehicle arrival time is around 762 seconds, or slightly less than 13 minutes.

Figure 19: Comparisons of DRT and PT/Car accessibility of the train station Saal an der Donau at 12:00 pm using different wait times, $\beta_0 = 71.82$, $\beta_1 = 0.119$

Maps a) and b) show the impact of lower or higher wait times in comparison to the PT accessibility, which remains constant. The extremely short wait time of 15 seconds widens the gap between the two, the low frequency of the buses creating journey times that are much longer. Only around the train station, where the accessibility is really by walking, and further east far from town, is it similar or higher. However even a considerably longer wait time doesn't create parity between the modes. The wait time of around 13 minutes is longer than the average ride duration with KEXI, but it appears travelling by PT is still slower. The yellow dot in the west is not explainable; it is located in the middle of the forest but has better PT accessibility than all of the surrounding points despite there not being a PT stop. The yellow area north of Kelheim is around a bus stop of a regional bus that goes to the train station. Again, it shows the influence of the chosen time on the PT accessibility; calculating it for 12:15 would likely create very different results on the outskirts of Kelheim, where the walking distance to the nearest DRT stop is further.

Especially map c) shows the effect of both the high ASC and the way walking is modelled. On the one hand, DRT accessibility in the service area is consistently higher than car accessibility, but these areas of lower car accessibility also extend into the surrounding forests. These are the areas furthest from roads leading quickly to the train station, which benefits the mode combination walk-DRT as the walk segment is teleported to the nearest DRT stop, thereby saving a lot of distance over walk-car, where the walk segment is only teleported to the nearest link permitting car traffic. Map d) is the first map where the average accessibility is higher for a mode other than DRT. The higher wait time and therefore higher trip duration lowers the DRT accessibility to a point where the higher ASC no longer compensates for it and in most of the service area the accessibility is very similar between the two modes.

4.5 Accessibility throughout the day

Independently of the wait time chosen, the distribution of the DRT accessibility stays the same, allowing a consistent ranking or comparison between different areas. The absolute values change, but the difference between one measuring point to the other stays constant. There is another factor, however, that complicates the comparison between different modes. Their interpretation hinges on the definitions and limitations of the DRT parameters and, in the case of PT, on the choice of observation time. While the DRT accessibility will also fluctuate throughout the day based on car traffic demand, the differences in PT accessibility are larger due to the time table. So far all accessibility calculations have been performed for 12:00 pm. For DRT, neither wait times nor travel times vary significantly throughout the day, so it can be assumed that the accessibility is representative of the accessibility for the rest of the day. To explore the size of the PT accessibility fluctuations, the accessibility is calculated for more points in time and the impact on the comparison with DRT is discussed.

The destinations chosen are doctors' offices. They have fixed opening hours, fully within both the operating hours of PT and DRT, appointments are equally likely throughout

the day and the time is often chosen by the staff rather than the patient. As timetables are often regular it seems unhelpful to calculate the accessibilities for every hour, as they would likely show similar patterns. Instead, nine random times⁷⁷ are generated between 08:00 and 17:00, which are assumed to be the average opening hours for a medical practice. When only considering the mean value for each time slot, there is little difference between them; they range from -0.62 to -0.73 utils. In other words, PT accessibility is more or less constant throughout the day when considering the whole town. The radial patterns of higher accessibility around bus stops in earlier maps have already hinted at what also occurs: islands of good accessibility form just before the departure of a bus and then disappear again. Figure 20 shows the range of accessibility values for each measuring point for both PT and DRT.

Figure 20: Range of PT and DRT accessibility of doctor's offices from 08:00 to 17:00

The city centre of Kelheim and the neighbourhood to the south of it have an even accessibility throughout the day. The close proximity to the doctors' offices and therefore the likelihood of walk trips most likely play a part in this. However, most bus lines also pass through the old town and/or along the main road past the shopping centre, so overall the frequency of PT in those areas is comparatively high. In the residential and industrial areas around the centre of Kelheim the fluctuation in PT accessibility is stronger, with a difference of up to 1.83 utils. Of course, these are only the extreme values of nine snapshots, but it certainly conveys a pattern. This pattern also makes sense from an organisational point of view: a limited number of buses and drivers serve the whole district, the lines go through the town centre in a hub and spoke system permitting interchanges, but areas that are not hubs consequently don't have a frequent public transport connection. The accessibility by DRT is predictably more even, with

⁷⁷08:37, 09:25, 10:05, 11:53, 13:41, 13:58, 14:15, 15:56, 16:25

some fluctuations on the South side of the river which likely experiences some congestion around the bridges at times.

Figure 21: Mean PT accessibility of doctor's offices from 08:00 to 17:00 and comparison to DRT

The mean accessibility of doctors is overall high, mostly due to their number and distribution throughout town. To make some of the differences visible, the legend has been adjusted and 0 utils is a dark green. Around most bus stops the accessibility is therefore positive, even if barely so for some of them. The accessibility is highest around the town centre and in Saal an der Donau, where most doctors are located and, in the case of the town centre, where most bus lines pass through. Compared to DRT, the accessibility is lower in all of the DRT service areas, and there are some areas with unexpectedly large negative differences. Apart from any other factors, the distribution of destinations favours the free-floating DRT. In the case of PT, the line route matters and while all areas seem to have good accessibility to some medical practices, the DRT offers a direct connection to all practices in town. So, some areas in the direct vicinity of a bus stop, that have comparatively good PT accessibility (i.e. northwest and southeast of the town centre) still have considerably better accessibility to doctors by DRT, therefore appearing dark red in the comparison map.

To summarise the findings up until now: the accessibility by DRT is an improvement over the accessibility by PT in both service areas. The size of the improvement depends on the definition of the wait time, ASC of DRT, and their spatial distribution on the time queried. The wait time can be chosen to represent different aspects or phases of waiting, reflecting the experiences of different users at different times. The DRT ASC is unusual in that it is positive and therefore also best describes the attitudes of a specific population

group. As it was calibrated using real-world data, one can assume however that it reflects the perspective of KEXI users well. When comparing the results to other modes though, especially car, this perspective needs to be taken into account when interpreting the results. If comparing to PT and, depending on the choice of destination to which the accessibility is calculated, it makes sense to choose different points in time or a time series. The PT accessibility fluctuates outside of the city centre and those neighbourhoods are part of the study area this needs to be accounted for.

4.6 Service Area 6: Hausen, Langquaid, Rohr and Herrngiersdorf

Service area 6 of the so-called LandKexi is made up of four municipalities in eastern Kelheim, bordering the district of Regensburg. They have been described in Chapter 2, but to sum it up briefly they have a low population density, a very high motorisation and few amenities. Like in the town of Kelheim regional buses pass through and connect the villages, but always with a very low frequency and a focus on transporting students to and from school. There are no train stations in the service area but one regional bus line directly connects Langquaid to Regensburg three times a day. For the following accessibility calculation, it is assumed that the service works as it does in the town of Kelheim: any relation between the DRT stops can be requested on-demand and requests will be rejected if there are no vehicles available, leading to a reasonable wait time for users who book a seat. The distance between the main villages is between 5 and 10 km along roads with a high speed limit, so a 20-minute wait time is presumed realistic. The other parameters stay the same.

Figure 22 show first the mean DRT and PT accessibility between 08:00 and 17:00 and then the range for each measuring point. For a comparison with PT it made sense to run the calculations for more time slots again, as the regional bus network is even thinner in this area. The maximum DRT accessibility is 0.57 utils; in this case, the higher wait time and longer distances lower the accessibility despite the multiple destinations. The lowest values are outside of the service area. In the service area, the DRT accessibility is highest around each stop and then decreases in a radial gradient. The same happens in the PT map, albeit for fewer stops. Here only the main villages have an accessibility comparable to DRT, and in the municipality without a supermarket, the values reach -8. Maps c) and d), visualising the range, show a constant DRT service and a PT accessibility that fluctuates in some areas, both those with a high and low mean accessibility. The longer distances make the ranges larger, due to the value in areas of low PT accessibility being mostly based on walk utility.

All four maps also have something in common. As they are right now, it is difficult to discuss the accessibilities on a more nuanced level. Recalling the distribution of settlements in this area, most of the space is agricultural land or forest. The accessibility to supermarkets or other amenities from there is irrelevant, but the results influence both the overall look of the map and the summarised values. The point of the accessibility calculation is to look at the accessibility for people and to evaluate their mobility

Figure 22: Mean and range of DRT and PT accessibility of supermarkets from 08:00 to 17:00

opportunities and limitations, but the inclusion of non-settlement areas blurs the results. Both of the lowest values are located outside of settlements and the accessibility is much more even there as well. The scale of the maps is another issue. The measuring points are placed in a grid every 200 m, the same resolution as for the town Kelheim, but the larger area forces a smaller scale to fit the page. The solution for the first part of the issue is to only consider measuring points of grid cells that contain buildings and those that are within the service area. To this end, the buildings layer is downloaded from Open Street Map and intersected with the grid. The definition of building is quite broad (e.g. the dataset contains barns), but still excludes more than two-thirds of the measuring points.

Figure 23 shows the remaining measuring points. Not surprisingly they have a higher average accessibility with both DRT and PT than before. The maps also show the distribution of stops and this is the first time the difference between the two becomes obvious: nearly all settlements have a DRT stop. Some of these settlements are so small they aren't even visible behind their DRT stop. The stops are also distributed across the larger villages, ensuring short walking distances. The bus stops on the other hand much less so. Many settlements don't have a bus stop at all or only have one close-by on the main road and passengers are expected to walk there. The same applies to the larger villages, which have fewer, mostly central bus stops that passengers have to walk to. As discussed in Chapter 2 it can likely be assumed that every household in this area with the financial and physical means has at least one motorised vehicle. Especially the aspect of physical ability will become more relevant in the future as the population significantly ages. Lowering the walking distance to the nearest transport stop therefore becomes key in guaranteeing the ability to utilise the offered mobility.

To overcome some of the visual barriers caused by the smaller scale, the distribution of accessibility values can also be summarised in a diagram. It removes some of the spatial components but permits clearer comparisons between different scenarios that don't rely on comparing the colour hues of small dots. The mean accessibility is calculated for every mode and remaining measuring point and counted for each municipality. In all four municipalities the car accessibility is between 0 and -1 at most measuring points. In Langquaid, which has two supermarkets, the accessibility can also be positive. All municipalities also have measuring points with a car accessibility of around -3 or less. Some of them are likely caused by the inclusion of utility buildings, however, all municipalities also have remote clusters of farmsteads that legitimately might have a lower accessibility even by private car.

DRT accessibilities are distributed independently of the car accessibilities, which is somewhat different from the situation in the town of Kelheim. The high density of the DRT stops there mean that the access walk to DRT is short and consequently, the trip duration is always similar to the sum of car travel time and the wait time. The longer access walks in this service area create a larger range of DRT accessibility, for example in Hausen. In Herrngiersdorf the DRT accessibility is noticeably lower than in the other municipalities despite a good distribution of DRT stops. This also coincides with a somewhat patchy car accessibility, mostly due to an indirect network of narrow rural

Figure 23: Mean DRT and PT accessibility of supermarkets from 08:00 to 17:00, measuring grid cells with buildings

Figure 24: Distribution of accessibility of supermarkets in settled areas by mode and municipality

roads. The improvements in accessibility by DRT over PT are therefore also lowest in Herrngiersdorf, as all modes are hindered by the same infrastructure.

The overall lowest PT accessibility to supermarkets is found in Hausen, which is also the municipality without a supermarket directly in their territory. Another factor is the structure of the PT network: the main corridor is Rohr i.NB over Hausen to Saal an der Donau, therefore the reachable supermarkets are the one in Rohr i.NB and one more in a village to the north (which is also included in the accessibility calculations but located outside of the map view). The connection to Langquaid and Herrngiersdorf is weaker, the accessibility to the supermarkets there is therefore also lower. It is likely that some of the PT accessibility in the other municipalities is also walk accessibility. How much is hard to determine, but the radial decrease in accessibility around the supermarkets is an indicator.

Another destination that is considered is sports clubs and facilities. Sports clubs fulfil important social functions beyond the opportunity to participate in physical exercise. They are active in the local happenings and offer a community and network.⁷⁸ As seen in Figure 3, a lot of villages have sports clubs. The focus is mostly on football and shooting,

⁷⁸Feiler and Breuer 2023, cf.

Figure 25: Distribution of accessibility of sport facilities in settled areas by mode and municipality

but many also offer other classes or groups like zumba or hiking. The actual sports facilities are used as destinations. If several sports fields are grouped together they are counted as one. This approach is used to account for sports fields often being located on the edge of the village, while the club itself might use an address in the centre. The accessibility by car is positive at the majority of measuring points in all four municipalities. The DRT accessibility is more mixed, and especially in Langquaid the range is very large — larger than the range of PT accessibility. The reason is likely a mixture of there being few sports facilities in Langquaid itself in combination with sports facilities outside of the service area which can be accessed only by PT. The decentralisation of sports facilities improves their accessibility in comparison with supermarkets in both Hausen and Rohr. The values are overall higher (which of course also has to do with the number of facilities) but they also bunch closer together. The improvement of DRT over PT is less pronounced, likely because a decent share of the population can walk to at least one sports facility. This raises the PT accessibility while lowering the DRT accessibility as fewer trips include the DRT ASC.

4.7 Accessibility index of everyday needs

One question of this work is if and how DRT can help improve the accessibility in peri-urban spaces. Better accessibility is not a goal in itself but it has the larger purpose of allowing people to satisfy their everyday needs. So far, only one type of destination is considered at a time. In our daily lives we travel to a variety of them though, and any one impacts our overall accessibility. The amenities that have been considered up until now are the train station, supermarkets, doctors and sports facilities. The maps in Chapter 2 also show pharmacies and public facilities. Work and school are major reasons for travel, but work is difficult to locate and a high percentage of employees commute outside of the service area while schools are served by school buses. Shopping in general can also be considered an everyday need or activity, and access to shopping opportunities is relevant, but it is also difficult to define which shops should be included and which ones are too niche. The larger villages have an assortment of boutiques and other small retail, however not enough to balance out the fact that they most probably have a very narrow customer base. On a more practical level, there is also the issue that the OpenStreetMap data for private retail in the area is incomplete. Instead, public and cultural amenities like town halls, libraries, post offices and community centres are included to represent both official errands as well as the accessibility to cultural and social events. In a separate run, churches are considered, less for their function as a place of worship, but again as a community event space.

In the case of the town of Kelheim the train station is clearly an important destination, the interchange to trains allowing travel to the regional centres for all kinds of purposes. There is no comparable station in eastern Kelheim: Depending on the origin either the train station in Saal an der Donau or a train station east of Langquaid, in the district of Regensburg, are closest. As of right now, the DRT accessibility contribution does not incorporate the changing of modes between DRT and PT, meaning that it is not possible to calculate the DRT accessibility to either the train stations or even Regensburg itself. This would have been useful as a way to represent the accessibility to amenities that don't exist within the service area.

For the figures 26 and 27 the accessibility at 12:00 to supermarkets, doctors, pharmacies as well as sports and other public facilities is calculated. The mean and median are calculated for each mode and measuring point. The mean PT accessibility is noticeably worse in all municipalities than in earlier diagrams for individual destinations. As it was only calculated for one moment in time, the impact of the low bus frequency is larger. Especially for Hausen and Rohr it is very probable that most of the PT accessibility is in reality walk accessibility, as it has lowered drastically. The DRT and car accessibility is consistent with earlier results. This makes sense as many of the destinations have similar distributions: with the exception of sports facilities most of them are located on the main streets in Langquaid and Rohr and the addition of public facilities has not changed this. What does change it, however, is the inclusion of churches. Like sports facilities, they are spatially distributed and the average distance between the measuring point and the church is therefore shorter. They are usually located in the village centres, close to

Figure 26: Distribution of mean accessibility of everyday needs at 12:00 in settled areas by mode and municipality

Figure 27: Distribution of median accessibility of everyday needs at 12:00 in settled areas by mode and municipality

DRT stops. As all destination types are weighed the same, their comparatively higher accessibility significantly increases the mean.

Figure 27 shows the median accessibility instead of the mean. There is little difference in the car accessibility but both DRT and PT accessibility change. The median PT accessibility in Hausen is a lot lower, suggesting that a few higher values raised the mean. This is most likely the accessibility to sports facilities which in Hausen is quite good due to their numbers and spatial distribution. The opposite happens for the other municipalities, Langquaid and Rohr especially. There, the accessibility to most destinations is high, but Langquaid has comparatively low accessibility to sports facilities and Rohr neither has a doctor nor the public transport connections at that moment in time to reach one. The median DRT accessibility is closer to the car accessibility in all municipalities, the reason being the low number of medical practices in the service area, which doesn't affect cars.

Overall the accessibility of every day needs hinges on their definition and also on their weight. While accessibility of sports and other public facilities is key to social participation, it is surely less important than accessibility to a supermarket or a pharmacy. Schwarze in his dissertation presents and compares different approaches and accessibility indices that are used in the planning practice.⁷⁹ They usually additionally include workplaces, schools and also often city centres. Especially workplaces and city centres would be important to look at in Kelheim as they are named as reasons for car usage and the lack of alternative connection criticised in the local development plan. To do this for this service area it would be necessary to be able to calculate the intermodal accessibility as the access to a train station cannot be used as a substitute. In the case of workplaces, which are not necessarily located in the city centre but also industrial and commercial developments elsewhere in the city region, this would also increase the accuracy.

⁷⁹Schwarze 2014, p. 67ff, p. 294ff.

5 Reflections and conclusion

At the beginning of this work Caruso⁸⁰ was cited, who defined peri-urban spaces as having a rural character but being under urban influence, referring to strong links to urban centres including significant commuting. The landscape might be rural, but their daily lives connect the inhabitants to the cities around them. By car workplaces, doctors or a variety of retail are barely 30 minutes away, but without it are time-consuming to access at all. Whatever cause or effect, the motorisation is very high and the public transport supply low. There is a great demand for public transport options both to travel within the town of Kelheim and also to connect to regional transport, as evidenced by the KEXI data. The number of trips leaving the four municipalities of service area no. 6 is likely even larger, as about 75 % of the working population commutes for to their job⁸¹. Linking back to Caruso: when only considering their settlement structure these municipalities are extremely rural, made up of a patchwork of small villages surrounded by mostly fields, but very few people actually still work in agriculture or forestry full time. Living there therefore by necessity requires commuting, which as of right now realistically needs to happen by private car for most people. The design of the service area, being limited to the four municipalities and not connecting to any higher frequency regional transport, doesn't help. The local development plan of the town of Kelheim also mentions the lack of connection between extensive residential developments around the town of Kelheim and the centre. This can only be partially confirmed though, as most of them are located outside of the KEXI service area as they technically belong to other municipalities. The analysis of origins and destinations does show however, that users input addresses outside of the service area and presumably walk the rest of the way.

In the last chapter public transport and DRT have mostly been talked about as if they were mutually exclusive. This is of course not true, the starting assumption of this work was that DRT could be a solution for rural or low-density public transport, which is also the way it is being used in Kelheim. DRT is an organisational form of transport which can be either public or private, public transport in the last chapter therefore meaning conventionally organised public transport with fixed lines and a time table. The separation stems primarily from the separation of the two in the MATSim model and to a certain point the institutional separation in the implementation, when in reality the user base is likely the same. While the Deutschlandticket is valid for KEXI, the process of booking and using the service is separate from the rest of the public transport. In Kelheim many users obviously use the service to change to and from the train, but with a rejection rate of 40 % this connection is not guaranteed. This leads to the question of what the expectations are of this new form of public transport. Cited arguments for DRT in general and in Kelheim specifically are flexibility, cost and resource efficiency as well as user comfort⁸². There is no doubt that the system is more flexible and offers more user comfort than a conventional bus line, discussions about on-demand and pre-booking

⁸⁰Caruso 2001, p. 12.

⁸¹Bayerisches Landesamt für Statistik 2023c.

⁸²Bayerischen Verwaltung für Ländliche Entwicklung 2023; Coutinho et al. 2020; Sörensen et al. 2021, cf.

notwithstanding. The cost efficiency however is an interesting topic: the data shows that few users generate a lot of the trips. At the same time the system has reached a limit and it is not possible to accommodate more users with a similar level of usage. Is this a conflict of objectives and/or uses? Detractors could argue that the system functions as a heavily subsidised taxi for a minority that is flexible enough to work with unpredictability. They would be right in so far, as that, as it stands, it is not the right solution for people on a fixed schedule and it is also too expensive for the municipality to afford without additional subsidies, which is why it will not be continued after 2025⁸³. Cost efficiency in comparison to conventional public transport is a topic that should be further investigated.

The KEXI data as well as the accessibility analyses show that DRT is very good at satisfying a spatially and temporally dispersed demand. To run efficient conventional public transport on the other hand this demand needs to be both spatially and temporally clustered. The issues arise when it is clustered in time but dispersed in space. For Kelheim this could be early morning trips to the train station in Saal or really any feeder service and most commuting trips. A limited number of vehicles cannot be everywhere at the same time, so it is not possible to transport a large number of people from all over town to catch the same train, for example. The DRT accessibility visualised in the maps can only ever be true for a limited number of measuring points at once before the wait time rises and the accessibility drops. This is different from the accessibility maps for the other modes: many more people can decide to use the system at the same time before there are noticeable effects like congested roads or vehicles.

The accessibility calculated is a spatial accessibility. For each measuring point, the question is what is the utility to travel from there to all destinations. It takes into account the transport system, the land use and can be specifically calculated for any point in time during the day. The results are highly spatially and temporally disaggregated and could have been even more so if necessary. Personal or individual aspects beyond the definition of the ASC are not included. This needs to be emphasised: as many peoples' daily lives bring them outside of the service area, their personal accessibility, as in the options and opportunities they have, looks very different. The limiting factors for calculating personal accessibilities as proposed by Kwan were data availability and realistically also the lack of integration of DRT with conventional PT in the model. For the same reason data for work places or shopping opportunities would not have lead to relevant results, as the DRT accessibility could only be properly calculated for the service area.

For the service area no. 6 the analyses have shown even before any transport system is taken into account, many amenities are simply not available or are far away. The fundamental problem therefore is the necessity to overcome large distances due to the lack of local infrastructure and here the distances are so large that even DRT reaches its limits in some cases. The proximity to larger cities offers solutions for those who can travel there by car, but if their life situation changes, they might not be able to provide their own basic needs any more unless they move. As the population ages, this will affect

⁸³Weigert 29.10.2024.

an increasing number of people. In early 2024 the EU parliament discussed and voted on a reform that would have required regular health and fitness to drive checks after a certain age⁸⁴. For many senior citizens in Kelheim, this could have meant the end of their independent living as there are no alternative solutions right now. The DRT results in all of these calculations have been much closer to the mode car than PT, but this version of the DRT system is also wishful thinking. The implemented system is much closer to the existing PT in frequency and route only with more stops. The analyses have also shown the positive impact of spatial dispersion on accessibility. Not only the existence of amenities, but also their location matters. Especially for public transport, the low frequency of the routes means that distance plays a much greater role, and nearby destinations can compensate for this as the walk accessibility is included. However, since most destinations are concentrated in a few places, the accessibility gap between public transport and DRT remains. The walk accessibility also plays a role for the DRT accessibility, but the important factor here is the increased number and distribution of DRT stops.

Distance is one aspect of trip duration, the other is wait time. For KEXI the average time between ride request and vehicle arrival is surprisingly short, the reason is likely a strict cut-off of which trips are accepted. Other ways to define the wait time based on KEXI data results in even shorter time spans. The service seems very good at planning and communicating the itinerary and thereby also managing the users expectations. The vehicles often arrive early, suggesting an internal time buffer to account for possible delays, and even minimal differences in departure time are communicated. For the modelling of DRT accessibility this means that compared to public transport the wait times are very low. On the one hand this makes sense as the users aren't waiting, but the flip side of the coin, rejected rides, aren't part of the analyses either. The assumed average wait time of 20 minutes for the DRT accessibility in service area no. 6 is realistic in the context of this logic. The impact of the wait time matters most in comparison with other modes. When only considering the distribution of DRT accessibility, comparing different areas with each other, the wait time applies for all measuring points equally and it can be neglected. If walk accessibility is included as an alternative for DRT, like it is in this model, it does however affect for which relations it is chosen instead. A longer wait time means more DRT accessibility values are really walk values. If assuming a DRT user base that is maybe elderly or uses DRT because they are physically unable to drive, this should be taken into account as the mode walk might not be a true alternative for them.

The MATSim accessibility contribution follows the overall logic of MATSim and defines the accessibility as the expected maximum utility. Accessibility is therefore also measured in utils. Several of the works cited in Chapter 2 have discussed the issue of communicability of accessibility measures⁸⁵. The combination of the logsum term, the abstract unit as well as parameters like the ASC make this difficult. The explicit meaning and consequences of the results for the transport system and the planning practice are unclear. They can only

⁸⁴Tagesschau 2024.

⁸⁵S. L. Handy and Niemeier 1997; Kwan 1998; Schwarze 2014, cf.

be deduced from context and by comparison. The presentation of the results gains in importance in order to facilitate interpretation. Spatially mapping the measuring points and using a colour gradient to represent the accessibility values visualises spatial patterns and can be combined with the stops and destinations. This interaction between transport system and territory becomes visible. It is limited by the range of colours chosen, which can influence the perception and highlight or hide differences. Choosing a colour scale where all positive values had the same colour proved impractical when considering only results with high accessibility but it made sense when comparing them to other, lower, results. The overlaid histograms focus the attention on the values and counts at the cost of losing the spatial context. Measuring points exist purely as numbers, without any additional information about the environment. Points in the village centre are lumped together with points far away from the next settlement. This works well as an addition to spatial mapping and if the fundamental assumption is made that the accessibility at each measuring point matters the same.

The public concern with public transport in Germany exists at the intersection of social and economic inclusion and the promotion of sustainable transport as part of efforts to reduce CO² emissions according to international agreements.⁸⁶ Accessibility through public transport is not simply a matter of physical proximity; it represents a fundamental aspect of social inclusion and equity. In small cities, where public transport networks may be limited, understanding and improving accessibility becomes critical to ensure that all members of the community have equal opportunities for mobility, economic participation and social engagement. Sustainable transport is not only environmentally responsible, it is also deeply related to social welfare, as it can reduce the economic burden on marginalised populations and foster community cohesion⁸⁷. At the same time political discourse is dominated by questions about funding and subsidies, or rather lack thereof, and many districts are struggling to find the financial resources to maintain or even improve their public transport⁸⁸. The KEXI service in the town of Kelheim was partially funded by additional subsidies, which are now running out. The city council voted nearly unanimously to not extend the service due to the high costs.⁸⁹ In this context, on-demand public transport with smaller vehicles promises a solution and a way forward for districts with a low demand. The flexible itineraries and lower maintenance cost for the vehicles could increase the cost efficiency while also improving the accessibility.

Their potential is determined by the type and number of destinations in the service area as well as its connections to the larger region. A dense network of stops offers quick access to the system everywhere, making local destinations highly accessible. However, as peri-urban areas are defined by commuting and local destinations may not be available, connections outside the service area are key. The definition of the service area should include a train station or regional bus lines with a high frequency. Even so, the capacity

⁸⁶Manderscheid 2021.

⁸⁷Farrington 2007.

⁸⁸Deutscher Städtetag 2024, cf.

⁸⁹Weigert 29.10.2024, p. 2.

of a small DRT system in a large area as a feeder service is limited due to time constraints. The use of DRT for commuting should be further investigated and integrated options with conventional public transport explored. Despite the probable issues as a feeder service, the connection and interplay between the different forms of public transport is crucial. They each have strengths and advantages that can and should play off each other.

These questions are and should also be part of a larger discussion about spatial development in the region. The district of Kelheim has had a positive population development for the last decades and the trend is projected to continue. This a favourable position to be in, as it also means more financial resources, yet it is likely that this growth will primarily happen in the form of mono-functional residential developments. The local strategy paper identifies the problems with these developments and uses the term '*doughnut effect*' to describe past development in Kelheim. However, the same document also expresses the need to designate more land for development in order to attract young families. Spatial development and transport planning are not being thought together and despite the identification of a problem, no consequences are drawn for the future. This makes the goal of better accessibility for all a battle against windmills and is symptom of the broader issue of districts and municipalities competing against each other for people and businesses to maintain their financial resources. Integrated regional planning needs to be strengthened and measures coordinated beyond and across departments and administrative boundaries. That said, DRT as an organisational form of public transport offers great potential for peri-urban regions. Private cars are the most efficient mode of transport from an individual point of view and will remain it for a while longer until DRT can be fully automated, but even until then DRT is a way to provide mobility options for those that don't drive, on relations and at times where it would be inefficient to run a conventional bus.

References

- Aberle, Christoph (2020). “Who Benefits from Mobility as a Service? A GIS-Based Investigation of the Population Served by Four Ride-Pooling Schemes in Hamburg, Germany”. In: *KN - Journal of Cartography and Geographic Information* 70.1, pp. 25–33. ISSN: 2524-4957. DOI: 10.1007/s42489-020-00041-4.
- Alonso-González, María J. et al. (2018). “The Potential of Demand-Responsive Transport as a Complement to Public Transport: An Assessment Framework and an Empirical Evaluation”. In: *Transportation Research Record: Journal of the Transportation Research Board* 2672.8, pp. 879–889. ISSN: 0361-1981. DOI: 10.1177/0361198118790842.
- Bayerischen Verwaltung für Ländliche Entwicklung (2023). *Flexibel und umweltfreundlich - mit KEXI On-Demand-Service im Landkreis Kelheim*. URL: <https://klimachancen.bayern/projekte/74/flexibel-und-umweltfreundlich-mit-kexi>.
- Bayerisches Landesamt für Statistik (2023a). *Amtliche Statistik*. URL: <https://www.statistik.bayern.de/>.
- (2023b). *Einwohnerzahlen am 30. September 2023*. URL: https://www.statistik.bayern.de/mam/produkte/veroeffentlichungen/statistische_berichte/a1200c_202343.pdf.
- (2023c). *Sozialversicherungspflichtig beschäftigte Arbeitnehmer in Bayern und deren Pendlerverhalten am 30. Juni 2023*. URL: https://www.statistik.bayern.de/mam/produkte/veroeffentlichungen/statistische_berichte/a6c00c_202300.pdf.
- BMVI (2016). *Mobilitäts- und Angebotsstrategien in ländlichen Räumen*. URL: <https://bmdv.bund.de/SharedDocs/DE/Publikationen/G/mobilitaets-und-angebotsstrategien-in-laendlichen-raeumen-neu.html>.
- (2018). *Mobilität in Deutschland*.
- Bundesinstitut für Bau-, Stadt- und Raumforschung, ed. (2019). *Methodische Weiterentwicklungen der Erreichbarkeitsanalysen des BBSR*. URL: https://www.bbsr.bund.de/BBSR/DE/veroeffentlichungen/bbsr-online/2019/bbsr-online-09-2019-dl.pdf?__blob=publicationFile&v=1.
- Bundesministerium für Verkehr und digitale Infrastruktur (2018). *Regionalstatistische Raumtypologie des BMVI für die Mobilitäts- und Verkehrsforschung: Arbeitspapier*. URL: https://bmdv.bund.de/SharedDocs/DE/Anlage/G/regiostar-arbeitspapier.pdf?__blob=publicationFile.
- BVG (2024). *Flexible Fahrt mit dem BVG Muva*. URL: <https://www.bvg.de/de/verbindungen/bvg-muva/flexible-fahrt>.
- Caruso, Geoffrey (2001). *Periurbanisation, the situation in Europe: a bibliographical note and survey of studies in the Netherlands, Belgium, Great Britain, Germany, Italy and the Nordic Countries*. URL: <https://orbilu.uni.lu/handle/10993/10153>.
- CleverShuttle (21.07.2023). *CleverShuttle*. URL: <https://www.clevershuttle.de/>.
- Coutinho, Felipe Mariz et al. (2020). “Impacts of replacing a fixed public transport line by a demand responsive transport system: Case study of a rural area in Amsterdam”. In: *Research in Transportation Economics* 83, p. 100910. ISSN: 07398859. DOI: 10.1016/j.retrec.2020.100910.

- Deutscher Städtetag (2024). *Bund muss jetzt Farbe bekennen: Investitionen in den Nahverkehr*. URL: <https://www.staedtetag.de/presse/pressemeldungen/2024/oepnv-investitionen-bund-muss-farbe-bekennen>.
- Diepolder, Severin et al. (2024). “On the Computation of Accessibility Provided by Shared On-Demand Mobility”. In: DOI: 10.21203/rs.3.rs-4803855/v1.
- Farrington, John H. (2007). “The new narrative of accessibility: its potential contribution to discourses in (transport) geography”. In: *Journal of Transport Geography* 15.5, pp. 319–330. ISSN: 09666923. DOI: 10.1016/j.jtrangeo.2006.11.007.
- Feiler, Svenja and Christoph Breuer (2023). “Deutschland: Sportvereine als wichtige Akteure der Zivilgesellschaft”. In: *Funktionen von Sportvereinen in europäischen Gesellschaften*. Ed. by Siegfried Nagel et al. Cham: Springer International Publishing and Imprint Springer Gabler, pp. 133–165. ISBN: 978-3-031-27714-6. DOI: 10.1007/978-3-031-27715-3_6.
- Geurs, Karst T. and Bert van Wee (2004). “Accessibility evaluation of land-use and transport strategies: review and research directions”. In: *Journal of Transport Geography* 12.2, pp. 127–140. ISSN: 09666923. DOI: 10.1016/j.jtrangeo.2003.10.005.
- Handy, S. L. and D. A. Niemeier (1997). “Measuring Accessibility: An Exploration of Issues and Alternatives”. In: *Environment and Planning A: Economy and Space* 29.7, pp. 1175–1194. ISSN: 0308-518X. DOI: 10.1068/a291175.
- Handy, Susan (1996). “Methodologies for exploring the link between urban form and travel behavior”. In: *Transportation Research Part D: Transport and Environment* 1.2, pp. 151–165. ISSN: 13619209. DOI: 10.1016/S1361-9209(96)00010-7.
- Hansen, Walter G. (1959). “How Accessibility Shapes Land Use”. In: *Journal of the American Institute of Planners* 25.2, pp. 73–76. ISSN: 0002-8991. DOI: 10.1080/01944365908978307.
- Hernández, Diego (2012). “Activos y estructuras de oportunidades de movilidad: Una propuesta analítica para el estudio de la accesibilidad por transporte público, el bienestar y la equidad”. In: *EURE (Santiago)* 38.115, pp. 117–135. ISSN: 0250-7161. DOI: 10.4067/S0250-71612012000300006.
- infas Institut für angewandte Sozialwissenschaft GmbH (2018). *Mobilität in Deutschland - Ergebnisbericht*. Ed. by Bundesministerium für Verkehr und digitale Infrastruktur. Bonn.
- International Transport Forum (n.d.). *International Experiences on Public Transport Provision in Rural Areas: Case-Specific Policy Analysis*. URL: https://www.itf-oecd.org/sites/default/files/docs/15cspa_ruralareas.pdf.
- ioki (2023). *Ioki und VHH setzen On-Demand-Mobilität gemeinsam fort*. URL: <https://ioki.com/ioki-und-vhh-setzen-on-demand-mobilitaet-gemeinsam-fort/>.
- Knie, Andreas et al. (2020). *Ride-Pooling-Dienste und ihre Bedeutung für den Verkehr. Nachfragemuster und Nutzungsmotive am Beispiel von "CleverShuttle" - eine Untersuchung auf Grundlage von Buchungsdaten und Kundenbefragungen in vier deutschen Städten*. URL: <https://www.econstor.eu/handle/10419/220020>.
- Kwan, Mei-Po (1998). “Space-Time and Integral Measures of Individual Accessibility: A Comparative Analysis Using a Point-based Framework”. In: *Geographical Analysis* 30.3, pp. 191–216. ISSN: 00167363. DOI: 10.1111/j.1538-4632.1998.tb00396.x.

- Landkreis Kehlheim (1.05.2023). *Anlage zur Vorabkennzeichnung über öffentliche Personenverkehrsdienste mit Kraftfahrzeugen im Landkreis Kelheim im Land KEXI on-demand-Verkehr*. URL: https://www.landkreis-kelheim.de/media/12798/eu-vo-veroeffentlichung_2022_land_kexi.pdf.
- (n.d.). *Kexi - Dein Expressbus im Landkreis Kelheim*. URL: <https://kexi.de>.
- Landratsamt Kelheim (2018). *Handlungskonzept Regionalmanagement Landkreis Kelheim: Mobiler innovativer Lebens- und Wirtschaftsstandort*. Kelheim.
- Lokale Aktionsgruppe Landkreis Kelheim e.V. (2023). *Lokale Entwicklungsstrategie (LES) Landkreis Kelheim*. Ed. by Landkreis Kehlheim. URL: <https://www.voef.de/media/14036/les-lag-landkreis-kelheim-zusammenwachsen-und-zusammen-wachsen-2023.pdf>.
- Manderscheid, Katharina (2021). “Nachhaltige Mobilität: Eine soziologische Dimensionalisierung”. In: *Soziologie der Nachhaltigkeit*. transcript Verlag, pp. 417–434. ISBN: 9783839451991. DOI: 10.1515/9783839451991-022.
- Mehlert, Christian and Martin Schiefelbusch (2017). “Mobility on-demand: Disruption oder Hype - Entwicklung und Zukunft von Rufbus, Sharing und Robotaxi”. In: *Nahverkehr* 35.7+8, pp. 6–12.
- Meyer, Jonas et al. (2017). “Autonomous vehicles: The next jump in accessibilities?” In: *Research in Transportation Economics* 62, pp. 80–91. ISSN: 07398859. DOI: 10.1016/j.retrec.2017.03.005.
- MOIA (21.07.2023). *Dein Ride-Sharing Service für die Mobilität der Zukunft*. URL: <https://www.moia.io/de-DE>.
- Monzón de Cáceres, Andrés (1988). “La accesibilidad individual como elemento de evaluación de los planes de transporte en la comunidad de Madrid/España”. In: *Informes de la Construcción* 40.396, pp. 21–38. ISSN: 0020-0883. DOI: 10.3989/ic.1988.v40.i396.1549.
- Nahmias-Biran, Bat-hen et al. (2021). “Evaluating the impacts of shared automated mobility on-demand services: an activity-based accessibility approach”. In: *Transportation* 48.4, pp. 1613–1638. ISSN: 0049-4488. DOI: 10.1007/s11116-020-10106-y.
- Nicolai, Thomas W. and Kai Nagel (2014). “High resolution accessibility computations”. In: *Accessibility and Spatial Interaction*. Ed. by Ana Condeço-Melhorado, Aura Reggiani, and Javier Gutiérrez. Edward Elgar Publishing. ISBN: 9781782540731. DOI: 10.4337/9781782540731.00010.
- Pereira, Rafael H. M. et al. (2021). “r5r: Rapid Realistic Routing on Multimodal Transport Networks with R 5 in R”. In: *Findings*. DOI: 10.32866/001c.21262.
- Regionaler Planungsverband Regensburg (2020). *Regionalplan Region Regensburg*. URL: https://www.regierung.oberpfalz.bayern.de/service/landes_und_regionalplanung/regionalplanung/index.html.
- Schwarze, Björn (2014). “Eine Methode zum Messen von Naherreichbarkeit in Kommunen”. Dissertation.
- Siedentop, Stefan, Sebastian Roos, and Stefan Fina (2013). “Ist die „Autoabhängigkeit“ von Bewohnern städtischer und ländlicher Siedlungsgebiete messbar?” In: *Raumforschung und Raumordnung* 71.4, pp. 329–341. ISSN: 1869-4179. DOI: 10.1007/s13147-013-0240-0.

- Son, Jong-Hun et al. (2022). “Investigating the Spatiotemporal Imbalance of Accessibility to Demand Responsive Transit (DRT) Service for People with Disabilities: Explanatory Case Study in South Korea”. In: *Journal of Advanced Transportation* 2022, pp. 1–9. ISSN: 0197-6729. DOI: 10.1155/2022/6806947.
- Sörensen, Leif et al. (2021). “How much flexibility does rural public transport need? – Implications from a fully flexible DRT system”. In: *Transport Policy* 100, pp. 5–20. ISSN: 0967-070X. DOI: 10.1016/j.tranpol.2020.09.005. URL: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0967070X19309709>.
- Statistisches Bundesamt (2023). *RegioStaR nach Fläche, Bevölkerung und Bevölkerungsdichte am 31.12.2022*. URL: <https://www.destatis.de/DE/Themen/Laender-Regionen/Regionales/Gemeindeverzeichnis/Administrativ/15-regiostar.html>.
- (2024). *Amtliche Statistik*. URL: https://www.destatis.de/DE/Home/_inhalt.html.
- Tagesschau (2024). *Kommen Gesundheitschecks für ältere Autofahrer?* URL: <https://www.tagesschau.de/ausland/europa/eu-gesundheit-fuehrerschein-wissing-blockade-100.html>.
- Verkehrsgemeinschaft Landkreis Kelheim (2024). *Wabenplan*. URL: https://www.landkreis-kelheim.de/media/11994/wabenplan_01012024.pdf.
- Wehmeier, Thomas, ed. (n.d.). *ÖPNV in nachfrageschwachen Räumen*.
- Weigert, Beate (29.10.2024). “Als Erstes gab es in Kelheim den Rufbus Kexi – nun schafft die Stadt ihn wieder ab”. In: *Mittelbayerische* 2024. URL: <https://www.mittelbayerische.de/lokales/landkreis-kelheim/als-erstes-gab-es-in-kelheim-den-rufbus-kexi-nun-schafft-die-stadt-ihn-wieder-ab-17310176>.
- Ziemke, Dominik and Joschka Bischoff (2023). “Accessibilities by shared autonomous vehicles under different regulatory scenarios”. In: *Procedia Computer Science* 220, pp. 747–754. ISSN: 18770509. DOI: 10.1016/j.procs.2023.03.099.
- Zwick, Felix and Kay W. Axhausen (2022). “Ride-pooling demand prediction: A spatiotemporal assessment in Germany”. In: *Journal of Transport Geography* 100, p. 103307. ISSN: 09666923. DOI: 10.1016/j.jtrangeo.2022.103307.